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Co-author(s):	G. Paludetto, C. Rodio, R. Lazzari, Z. Feng (UoS), A. Kontou, A. G. Paspatis, P. Kotsampopoulos (ICCS), O. Gehrke (DTU), T.A. Zerihun (SINTEF), A.G. Acosta (RWTH), E. Rikos (CRES), V. Subramaniam Rajkumar (TUD)
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List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
API	Application Programming Interface
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
BMS	Battery Management System
CHIL	Controller Hardware-In-the-Loop
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CM	Configuration Management
CRES	Center For Renewable Energy Sources
CSC	Centralised Supervisory Controller
CSV	Comma Separated Values
CVC	Coordinated Voltage Control
DDPG	Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DHN	District Heating Network
DPSL	Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
DRTS	Digital Real-Time Simulation
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DTU	Technical University of Denmark
EHP	Electrical Heat Pump
ESS	Energy Storage Systems
FBF	FeedBack Filtering
FMI	Functional Mock-up Interface
GD	Geographically Distributed
GDRTS	Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulation
GDS	Geographically Distributed System
GDSim	Geographically Distributed Simulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
HIL	Hardware-In-the-Loop
IA	Interface Algorithm
iasC	Infrastructure-as-Code
ICCS	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IT	Information Technology
ITM	Ideal Transformer Model
JaNDER	Joint test facility for smart energy Networks with Distributed Energy Resources
JRA	Joint Research Activity
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LPF	Low-Pass Filter
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
LV	low-voltage
MDP	Markov Decision Process
NTP	Network Time Protocol
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens
PA	Power Amplifier
PCC	Point of Common Coupling
PDF	Probability Density Function
PF	Power Factor

PHIL	Power-Hardware-In-the-Loop
PNDC	Power Networks Demonstration Centre
PSI	Phase Shifting Impedance
PV	Photovoltaic
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
OLTC	On-Load Tap Changer
RES	Renewable Energy Source
REST	representational state transfer
RI	Research Infrastructure
RMS	Root Mean Square
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
RSE	Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico
RTDS	Real Time Digital Simulator
RTS	Real Time Simulation
RWTH	Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen
SDFT	Sliding Discrete Fourier Transform
SINTEF	Stiftelsen for industriell og teknisk forskning
SISO	Single-Input-Single-Output
SIL	Software-in-the-Loop
SoC	State-of-Charge
SoI	System of Interest
TA	Transnational Access
TEC	Tecnalia
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TSO	Transmission System Operator
TUD	Technische Universiteit Delft
uAPI	Universal Application Programming Interface
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UoS	University of Strathclyde
V-ITM	Voltage Type-Ideal Transformer Model
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VSIDC	Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation
VSI	Virtual Shifting Impedance
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The advanced methods and services developed within the ERIGrid 2.0 project to enhance RI capabilities. This document outlines the efforts made to showcase and assess the tools and services offered by the extended ERIGrid 2.0 RI. The extended infrastructure incorporates simulators, Hardware-In-the-Loop (HIL) systems, and physical labs, significantly expanding the testing capabilities of a single facility. Furthermore, the integration of these RIs allows access to additional domains not locally available, potentially provided by other facilities in terms of simulation or physical components. As a result, the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium has facilitated the augmentation of the number of feasible test cases, effectively demonstrating the enhanced services provided by multi-RIs.

Commencing with the holistic test descriptions, the results of which are detailed in Deliverable D13.1, several test cases have been conducted through the integration of RIs, with results presented in Deliverable D13.2. Subsequently, the extended RI has been fully established. Within ERIGrid 2.0, experimental activities have been carried out, and their outcomes have been collected and described in this report, i.e., Deliverable D13.3. These experiments showcase various extended services, including simulation, HIL, laboratory facilities, and various combinations thereof. Different types of experiments have been considered, encompassing single-environment RIs (such as simulation-simulation and pure hardware-pure hardware) and multiple-environment RIs, which combine simulation, HIL, and pure hardware elements.

The objectives of this document are as follows:

- (i) To demonstrate the ability of the extended RI to provide new services;
- (ii) To evaluate the results of the tests conducted to demonstrate the capability of the extended RI and highlight its advantages;
- (iii) To assess the set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), as defined in Deliverable D13.1, used to evaluate the capabilities of the extended RI achieved through the developed advanced methods and services.

The document begins by providing an overview of the demonstrations, which were developed in Deliverable D13.1, along with their detailed requirements and the results illustrating the extended RI's ability to offer new services. It then proceeds to present and analyse the outcomes obtained from the KPI questionnaires, as outlined in Deliverable D13.1. These questionnaires were designed to evaluate the extended capabilities of the RIs, consisting of a generic set of questionnaires applicable to all identified demonstrations, followed by demonstration-specific questionnaires for each of the individual demonstrations. Lastly, the document draws to a close by summarising the key findings and insights.

1 Introduction

The push towards achieving a sustainable energy supply is driven by the need to incorporate Renewable Energy Sources (RESs). However, the stochastic nature of renewable energy generation poses a challenge for energy utilities, making the operation of power grids more complex. Moreover, factors like technological advancements, controllable loads, integration with other energy sources, evolving regulatory policies, and market liberalisation necessitate adjustments in system operation. The foundation for transforming the existing power system into an intelligent entity, a smart grid, lies in well-designed operational concepts and intelligent automation.

While leveraging the advantages of these intelligent behaviours, it is expected that system-level developments and testing will play a significantly larger role in realising future solutions and technologies. Nevertheless, there is currently a gap in terms of proper validation approaches, concepts, and tools.

To address the challenge of integrating renewables, ERIGrid 2.0 expands and enhances the existing RI access. Serving as a centralised hub for researchers engaged in smart grids, smart energy systems, and renewable energy integration, it offers an extensive range of improved services, methods, and tools. This initiative aims to reinforce Europe's technical leadership in the energy sector and promote research and innovation to further solidify its prominent position.

1.1 Scope of the Document

Deliverable D13.3, titled “*D-JRA4.3 Demonstration of the Extended Research Infrastructure*” is the final deliverable of the integration and demonstration work of ERIGrid 2.0 project. It follows Deliverables D13.1 (*D-JRA4.1 Description of the Test Cases, 2023*) and D13.2 (*D-JRA4.2 Description of the Integrated Extended Research Infrastructure, 2023*) and highlights the endeavours undertaken to showcase and assess the tools and services provided by the extended ERIGrid 2.0 RI.

This document presents the outcomes of the integration and demonstration activities, which are dedicated to demonstrating and evaluating the services within the extended RI, respectively. The overarching objective is to contribute to the ERIGrid 2.0 project's main goal of “Provision of improved and integrated TA/VA services.” This contribution involves enhancing and expanding the RI services to better serve TA/VA users, enabling them to explore intricate configurations of smart grid and smart energy systems.

This report revisits the concept of the extended RI introduced in the previous Deliverables D13.1 and D13.2. This helps clarify the design of the set of advanced methods and services used for demonstration within the ERIGrid 2.0 project. Additionally, this document evaluates the set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), initially defined in Deliverable D13.1 in the form of questionnaires, developed to assess the performance of the extended capabilities of the RI.

1.2 Extended Research Infrastructure

The primary objective of ERIGrid 2.0 is to establish connections between RIs across Europe to conduct collaborative smart energy experiments. The goal is to harness the strengths and

expertise of each individual RI (Pellegrino et al., 2020). The approach of laboratory coupling enables the creation of synergies among different RIs. This involves sharing hardware, software assets, and the associated knowledge from multiple RIs, allowing for the execution of more advanced and intricate test cases on larger system configurations. This, in turn, promotes technological advancements aimed at realising the concept of virtually extended RIs.

1.3 Structure of the Document

This document is structured as follows. Section 2 offers an overview of all demonstrations and their corresponding results. Section 3 delves into the presentation and analysis of the results from the KPI questionnaires, which were developed to assess the extended capabilities of the RIs. The document concludes in Section 4.

Finally, additional information about the extended services as well as the KPIs Q&A are provided in the Appendix A and Appendix B.

2 Overview & Accomplishment of the Demonstrations

To provide the reader with context, this section offers a brief summary of the five demonstrations selected in the ERIGrid 2.0 project. These demonstrations aim to showcase and assess the services provided by the extended RI. Additionally, the section includes their detailed requirements and presents results that illustrate the extended RI's capacity to provide new services. Here is a brief overview of each demonstration and its primary objectives:

- 1. Improved Stability and Accuracy for PHIL:** This demonstration focuses on enhancing the accuracy and stability of Controller Hardware-In-the-Loop (CHIL) and PHIL experiments used for validating smart grid control schemes. It addresses the challenges of conducting real-time closed-loop experiments with real hardware, considering imperfections like delays and noise. The aim is to improve PHIL setup stability without compromising accuracy, benefiting applications in smart grids. In Section 2.1, the results of this demonstration are presented.
- 2. Time Delay Compensation for GDRTS:** Time delay is a crucial factor affecting the accuracy and stability of closed-loop GDRTS setups. This demonstration explores the compensation for time delay, which is deterministic yet variable in high-fidelity GDRTS setups. It also addresses the challenge posed by Geographically Distributed Systems (GDSs) interconnected over the Internet, where non-deterministic data exchange complicates time delay determination and compensation. The operational principles and results of this demonstration are further depicted in Section 2.2.
- 3. Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for Remote RI Testing:** This demonstration introduces tools to expedite the setup and coordination of highly distributed experiments, focusing on CVC as a use case. The algorithm manages network devices capable of regulating voltage, such as On-Load Tap Changers (OLTCs), BESS, and PV inverters. The objective is to showcase scalability by involving multiple labs in real-time simulations, PHIL, or CHIL resources. Detailed results are reported in Section 2.3.
- 4. Multi-Energy District Flexibility:** This demonstration explores the feasibility of power-to-heat service provision in a local multi-energy district and its impact on electric and thermal networks. It aims to provide flexibility requested by the Distribution System Operator (DSO) through a combination of electric and thermal storage systems, along with demand response from controllable loads like heat pumps and electric boilers. The heating system can offer services to the electrical system, such as congestion management and balancing power provision. A comprehensive summary of the achievements is reported in Section 2.4.
- 5. Alternating Current (AC) & Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Co-Simulation:** Smart grids involve complex interactions between the power system and ICT systems. To address this complexity, this demonstration focuses on co-simulation, enabling holistic evaluation of smart grid systems. Specifically, this demonstration aims to develop a co-simulation-based approach to test and characterise the tool used for interfacing AC and ICT systems, addressing the need for comprehensive cyber-physical simulation tools. Finally, Section 2.5 provides a detailed overview of the results.

2.1 Extended Range High-Fidelity PHIL Testing

Energy and power systems are transforming in a fast pace, integrating more and more new ICT technologies. This necessitates the testing of the algorithms, controllers and hardware, and the validation of their operation in conditions as close to real as possible. Moreover, the new technologies incorporate novel and complex algorithmic schemes thus they can exhibit dynamic behaviour and interactions with the rest of the power network that cannot be accurately captured based on pure simulations. Another constraint arises from intellectual property perspective, which means the exact implementation and operation of a piece of hardware might be unknown. At the same time, the testing should be in a controlled environment to minimise the risk of damaging the devices. For all the above reasons, RTS has attracted a lot of attention, as real hardware devices (controllers and power devices) can be interfaced with the Digital Real-Time Simulation (DRTS) in CHIL and PHIL setups, where the power system can be simulated and the dynamic behaviour of the device itself and its interactions with the rest of the system can be investigated.

Performing PHIL simulations can pose specific challenges that need to be considered prior to experimentation. More specifically, for the interface of a hardware device to the DRTS, a Power Amplifier (PA) unit is required (Lauss et al., 2015), a fact that can introduce additional dynamics to the original system and can cause instabilities and inaccuracies in the PHIL setup. As a result, an appropriate choice and coordination among the available coupling structures and interface algorithms needs to be ensured. Each coupling structure and interface algorithm inherits to the PHIL setup different dynamics, compromising either the overall's system stability, accuracy or range of testing scenarios. As a mitigation measure, stability augmentation methods and PHIL control algorithms can be utilised. One of the most commonly employed techniques to improve the stability of the PHIL setup is to implement a LPF on the hardware current measurement which is fed back into the DRTS to close the loop. Despite the fact that this FBF method has been found to be stabilising the PHIL setup, it reduces the accuracy of the system. To alleviate this need for low-pass filtering, advanced Interface Algorithms (IAs) are being investigated, aiming to realise at the same time stable and accurate PHIL testing, e.g. through optimal control and interface compensation approaches.

In the frame of Work Package (WP)11-Joint Research Activity (JRA)2 “Improved and Extended Real-Time/Co-simulation and HIL Tools” existing advanced interface algorithms were investigated and effort was given to combine them with the purpose of improving the stability and the accuracy of PHIL simulations, thus improving their applicability in validating modern power and energy systems. In that process, methods introducing a virtual series or parallel impedance through the interface algorithm or through shifting a part of the software impedance to the hardware side were in the focus of attention. However, it was revealed that the methods proposed to this day are not part of the original system of investigation and may thus lead to inaccurate results. On the other hand, shifting a part of impedance to the hardware requires having impedances of different values readily available at hand to perform multiple test cases, a stringent requirement for most research laboratories.

As a result of the research process, a novel interface algorithm, the Virtual Shifting Impedance method, was developed that enables to realise extended-range accurate and stable PHIL testing. The developed method suggests a virtual implementation of the shifting impedance algorithm. In order to prove the efficiency of the method, the analytical mathematical model was developed, extensive simulations were carried, and ultimately, demonstrations of this method took place. More information of the novel method can be found in the relevant journal publication (Paspatis et al., 2024).

In the following subsections, firstly the developed method is briefly described and then the demonstration of its efficiency and ability of providing extended RI services will be presented.

2.1.1 Virtual Shifting Impedance Algorithm

VSI is a novel stability enhancement interface algorithm that incorporates the principles of manipulation of interface signals and the manipulation of the impedance ratio. The forward interface signal, voltage in this case, is manipulated in the controller of the PA to represent the voltage after the shifted impedance. This manipulation of the interface signal emulates the physical shifting impedance and thereby improves the stability of the PHIL setup. The practical implementation of the approach is realised through the advanced control capabilities of modern PAs, where a virtual impedance algorithm within the inner control loop can realise the implementation of the VSI method.

Figure 1: (a) A representation of the PHIL setup, and (b) an equivalent PHIL interface modelling.

The initial software system impedance is:

$$Z_1 = R_1 + jX_1. \quad (1)$$

Aiming to shift a portion of Z_1 to the hardware System 2 (see Figure 1), inspired by (Kotsampopoulos, Lehfuss, Lauss, Bletterie, & Hatziargyriou, 2015), and assuming that the ratio of the shifted resistance is a , with $a \in (0, 1)$, then the new software system impedance is:

$$Z_{1n} = (1 - a)R_1 + j(1 - a)X_1. \quad (2)$$

Assuming the voltage after impedance Z_{1n} is V_D . With the software impedance reduced, the voltage after the original system impedance Z_1 is to be emulated by the PA to realise the virtual shift in impedance and ensure accurate simulation. In fact, the voltage V'_A can be obtained by subtracting the voltage drop across the shifted impedance $R_{SH} = aR_1$ and $X_{sh} = aX_1$ from V'_D as described in (Wu, Soeiro, Shekhar, Xu, & Bauer, 2021):

$$V'_{Ad} = V'_{Dd} - R_{SH}I_{Ad} + \omega_0 L_{SH}I_{Aq} - L_{SH} \frac{dI_{Ad}}{dt}, \quad (3)$$

$$V'_{Aq} = V'_{Dq} - R_{SH}I_{Aq} - \omega_0 L_{SH}I_{Ad} - L_{SH} \frac{dI_{Aq}}{dt}. \quad (4)$$

This makes it feasible to generate the voltage at the output of the shifted impedance by manipulating the reference voltage of the PA, without requiring the addition of any hardware impedance component in System 2 (see Figure 1).

The steady-state approximation of the virtual impedance implementation, widely used in inverter control schemes, can also be adopted to overcome practical implementation issues

Figure 2: VSI algorithm implementation.

(Wang, Li, Blaabjerg, & Loh, 2015; He & Li, 2011; Guerrero, de Vicuna, Matas, Castilla, & Miret, 2005). The inclusion of the transient (derivative) term in the control action can lead to possible amplification in noise, requiring a low-pass filter that can deteriorate the response of the proposed method. In addition, the incorporation of the derivative term also increases the computational burden significantly. Therefore, ignoring the derivative dynamic term, the reference voltage takes the form:

$$V'_{Ad} = V'_{Dd} - R_{SH}I_{Ad} + \omega_0 L_{SH}I_{Aq}, \quad (5)$$

$$V'_{Aq} = V'_{Dq} - R_{SH}I_{Aq} - \omega_0 L_{SH}I_{Ad}, \quad (6)$$

where V'_A is the manipulated reference voltage of the inner voltage control scheme of the PA and I_A is the current of the hardware system. The implementation of the VSI methodology is depicted graphically in Figure 2 that is practically implemented in the PA's control card, as shown with in Figure 1. The original impedance of the hardware system remains the same, i.e. $Z_2 = R_2 + jX_2$, without requiring the additive physical impedance, as it would in the Phase Shifting Impedance (PSI) method case.

The virtual impedance shifting implemented in (5) and (6) can be further modelled as an equivalent impedance (Z_{SH}), arising as an additional feedback loop to manipulate the reference signal of the power amplifier. The equivalent block diagram of the PHIL system with VSI method implemented is illustrated in Figure 4, whose open-loop transfer function is given by:

$$F_O^*(s) = e^{-sT_{d1}} T_{FW}(s) \frac{Z_1(s) - Z_{SH}(s)}{Z_2(s) + e^{-sT_{d0}} G_{VA}(s) Z_{SH}(s)} e^{-sT_{d0}} G_{VA}(s) T_{FB}(s) T_{CM}(s) e^{-sT_{d2}}. \quad (7)$$

Assuming the transfer functions of signal processing, measurement units and PA as unity and substituting $Z_{SH}(s) = aZ_1(s)$ into (7), the open-loop transfer function of VSI-based PHIL system can be written as:

$$F_O^*(s) = \frac{(1-a)Z_1(s)}{Z_2(s) + aZ_1(s)e^{-sT_{d0}}} e^{-s(T_{d0}+T_{d1}+T_{d2})}. \quad (8)$$

Accordingly, the system characteristic equation is given by:

$$1 + \frac{(1-a)Z_1(s)}{Z_2(s) + aZ_1(s)e^{-sT_{d0}}} e^{-s(T_{d0}+T_{d1}+T_{d2})} = 0. \quad (9)$$

According to the Nyquist stability criterion (Franklin, Powell, & Emami-Naeini, 2014), the minimum PHIL system stability margin is the shortest distance between $F_O^*(j\omega)$ and the critical point

Figure 3: Nyquist plot of the open-loop transfer function of the PHIL system with variable software impedance.

Figure 4: Equivalent block diagram of PHIL system with VSI.

$(-1, 0)$ in the polar diagram as presented in Figure 3. The condition for the minimum stability margin is achieved when the real-part of $F_O^*(j\omega)$ is greater than -1 , and can be represented as:

$$\Re \{ F_O^*(j\omega_0) \} + 1 > 0, \omega_0 = \left\{ \arg \min_{\omega \in \mathbb{R}} |1 + F_O^*(j\omega)| \right\}. \quad (10)$$

Using the condition for marginal stability, the minimum VSI ratio a can be determined. Substituting (7) into (10) yields the shifting impedance at marginal boundary for stabilising the PHIL system.

2.1.2 Experimental Results

The first set of experimental tests were conducted at the PNDC, University of Strathclyde. The experimental setup comprises a digital real-time simulator from RTDS technologies, a 270 kV A bi-directional power amplifier, and a 50 kV A passive load bank. The passive load presents an impedance range from 3Ω to 100Ω . For the purpose of experimental analysis, an impedance ratio of $Z_1 = Z_2 = 1 \Omega$ is chosen, with $Z_1 = Z_2 = 12 \Omega$. The topology of the experimental setup is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Overview of the PHIL experimental setup in PNDC laboratory.

Figure 6: PHIL experimental results with FBF and VSI methods.

In Figure 6 the experimental results for the PHIL setup with FBF and VSI are presented. In the two upper sub figures the voltages in case of FBF and VSI are demonstrated, while in the two bottom sub figures the corresponding currents for the two cases are presented. As can be observed, the PHIL system is marginally stable with the incorporation of a very strict LPF of cut-off frequency of 300 Hz. On the other hand, with an impedance shift of 16 %, the VSI approach exhibits a stable response in terms of the voltages and currents. To demonstrate the ability of the proposed VSI to deal with transients within the network, a step reduction of 8 % in voltage is induced at $t = 1.2\text{ s}$ and presented in Figure 7. As can be observed, the proposed VSI maintains stable operation during the transient. Finally, the active and reactive power transfer with VSI is shown in Figure 9.

(a) Voltage of the PHIL setup during voltage dip

(b) Current of the PHIL setup during voltage dip

Figure 7: PHIL experimental results with VSI method while performing a step change in software side voltage.

Figure 8: VSI-aided PHIL setups with different shifting impedance R_{sh} : (a) 1.0Ω ($a=8.3\%$), (b) 1.5Ω ($a=12.5\%$), (c) 2.0Ω ($a=16.7\%$), (d) 2.4Ω ($a=20.0\%$), and (e) 3.0Ω ($a=25.0\%$).

The second set of experiments took place in DPSL laboratory of University of Strathclyde. The setup was similar to Figure 5, with the difference that a Triphase 90 kV A power amplifier and a 256-step passive load bank, were utilised. The hardware impedance used was $11.5 + j0.3141 \Omega$ while the software impedance was 12Ω .

Figure 9: Hardware side current behaviour of the LPF-based PHIL setup with cut-off frequency: (a),(b) 100 Hz; (c),(d) 75 Hz; (e),(f) 50 Hz.

Figure 10: Hardware side active power behaviour of the LPF-based PHIL setup with cut-off frequency: (a),(b) 100 Hz.

In Figure 9 the hardware current of PHIL setup is presented, when the FBF method is chosen for the stabilisation, for filters with cut-off frequency of 100 Hz, 75 Hz, and 50 Hz. Utilising FBF filters with such low cut-off frequency to stabilise the PHIL setup comes at the high expense of the overall accuracy. This can be witnessed in the measured active power of the setup Figure 10.

On the other hand, in Figure 8, the results when the VSI method is utilised, are presented. The scenarios when 8.3 %, 12.5 %, 16.7 %, 20 % and 25 % of software impedance sifting takes place, are demonstrated. As is evident, the implementation of the proposed VSI method mitigates

the active power oscillations of the PHIL setup to a lower level compared to the case of the PHIL setup without VSI. Moreover, with the impedance shifting ratio increment, the power signals tend to converge and present fewer oscillations. Moreover, even with a higher shifted impedance ratio, the VSI exhibits much better accuracy in relation to FBF method, enabling the possibilities for extended range – increased precision PHIL experimentation.

2.1.3 Advanced Hardware-in-the-loop Testing Chain for Investigating Interactions Between Smart Grid Components During Transients

Part of the research focused on suggesting a HIL testing procedure for the investigation of interactions between smart grid components during transient events. The proposed testing chain is directed towards both academic and industrial HIL users, e.g. relay manufacturers, power electronics manufacturers and DSOs/Transmission System Operators (TSOs). All different HIL simulation setups, ranging from simple local simulations up to more elaborate, geographically distributed HIL simulations, are discussed, forming a solid testing chain. Detailed information about this research work can be found in the relevant publication (Paspatis et al., 2024).

In Figure 12, the interactions that can be tested based on each type of chosen validation method along with the advantages and disadvantages are presented. In summary:

- **At Stage 1** (pure simulation) RTS and Software-in-the-Loop (SIL), the control and protection systems are considered ideal in the simulation environment, and average models are implemented. Moreover, multiple simulation software in the loop can be considered, while real-time and non-real-time implementations are also possible. This step is the very first validation step in which control states interactions with power system dynamics can be observed and identified.
- **At Stage 2** (CHIL) a piece of hardware controller or protection devices are connected to the DRTS and the control and protection strategies can be tested in real-time conditions, while validating at the same time the hardware controller limitations, transient interactions with simulated control and protection components and communication networks.
- **At Stages 3 and 4**, PHIL and Combined PHIL-CHIL, hardware power components can be employed to test the interactions between the controllers and the real devices, like photovoltaic systems, inverters, machines, etc. On top of that, industrial components can be tested as “black boxes”, overcoming the need for detailed or imperfect modelling.
- **At Stage 5**, Geographically Distributed HIL (GD RTS/HIL), the capabilities of remote labs can be harnessed and a more detailed representation of the power system and/or employing hardware devices that are available in different laboratories can be achieved.

Figure 11: Applications, components, and interactions to be tested at each chain step.

Chain stage	Applications / Test rationale	Pros & Cons	Interactions to be tested	Examples
RTS/SIL (1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> System operation 	(+) Flexibility in the design of scenarios (-) Inaccurate dynamics (noise in the measurements, time delays in controls, non-disclosed control, and power components)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Control states with power system states 	Investigation of a fault-ride-through algorithm during a grid-fault
CHIL (2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> System operation Controller verification Digital twins 	(+) Accurate controller behavior (+) Testing of non-disclosed control components (-) Inaccurate dynamics in the simulated system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hardware controller with power system states Hardware controller with control system states Protection relays with control operation Protection relays with power system operation 	Investigation of a supervisory controller operation with regards to communication latency
PHIL (3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> System operation Controller verification Converter/ machine operation validation Industrial components testing (non-disclosed) Digital twins 	(+) Accurate power hardware behavior (+) Testing of non-disclosed power components (-) Inaccuracies and time delays introduced by the amplification equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Power hardware operation with power system states Power hardware operation with industrial protection relays functions Power hardware with simulated power components 	Coordination between a supervisory controller and control settings of an industrial PV inverter
CHIL/PHIL (4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> System operation Controller verification Converter/ machine operation validation Industrial components testing (non-disclosed) Digital twins 	(+) Both controller and power hardware behavior accuracy (+) Testing of both control and power non-disclosed components (-) Increased complexity and required I/O resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Power hardware operation with industrial protection relays functions Hardware controllers with power hardware Energy management systems with power hardware Prototype power hardware with system-level controllers 	Investigation of the interactions between the controller of grid-following inverter and the operation of a real grid-forming inverter
GD RTS/HIL (5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> System operation Controller verification Converter/ machine operation validation Industrial components testing (non-disclosed) Digital twins 	(+) Extension of lab capabilities and supported test cases (-) Significant delays introduced by the communication network (internet) (-) Inappropriate for fast transients	Same as above but with components not available in the original lab.	Investigation of power sharing between grid-forming inverters using inverters not available in the original lab

Figure 12: Details on the chain steps, their applications, pros and cons, interactions to be tested, and examples.

Depending, on the testing scenarios and the type of hardware under test some of the above mentioned stages maybe be necessary or can be omitted. A discussion around this is built based on the Figure 11. When evaluating a converter controller, the first step is to assess its response to power system events through SIL testing. Then, CHIL testing allows the control scheme to be applied to a real microcontroller, examining its interactions with other control and protection schemes. PHIL testing further investigates interactions with the power hardware component, such as the converter itself, leading to potential optimisation of controller parameters and understanding interactions with power components with unknown controllers.

Similarly, microgrid controllers follow this testing progression. SIL and CHIL are the initial steps, with combined CHIL/PHIL used to study interactions between the microgrid controller and hardware power devices with undisclosed control algorithms. Finally (GD RTS/HIL) is employed to test microgrid controllers in systems containing models or devices not available locally. Protection schemes start with simulation evaluations and move to CHIL to examine interactions with other control schemes, or CHIL/PHIL for non-disclosed control schemes of power devices, with GD RTS/HIL offering a broader range of component testing. Hardware topologies, such as power electronics or machines, begin with simulation testing and progress to PHIL, typically using simple control schemes, rendering CHIL often unnecessary, while GD RTS/HIL may have limited transient response capabilities.

2.2 Time Delay Compensation for GDRTS

In pursuing net zero targets through ongoing energy transition and decarbonization efforts, the energy system has experienced a continuous expansion in terms of size, complexity, and diversity. This expansion is driven by the employment of active power network controls, the widespread adoption of converter-interfaced distributed generation, and the implementation of emerging power electronics techniques, among other contributing factors. Consequently, this not only poses a demand for developing advanced real-time simulation techniques capable of effectively characterising and emulating such complex systems under a significantly wider range of operational conditions but also presents a significant challenge for individual RI in effectively validating these emerging complex energy systems. Hence, the real-time coupling and integration of geographically distributed RIs via the GDRTS approach has been developed to leverage the equipment, real-time simulations, and expertise of individual RI collaboratively to address the evolving needs for experimental validation of complex energy systems.

As illustrated in Figure 13, data and signals within the GDRTS setup are transmitted over the internet through a dedicated interface that bridges multiple RIs into a closed-loop configuration. The indeterministic nature of power signal data exchange over the internet not only introduces substantial time delay in the GDRTS closed-loop configuration but also poses a significant challenge in accurately characterising, quantifying, and subsequently compensating for this delay. In analogy to the conventional PHIL setups, the inherent time delay stemming from the GDRTS interfacing system is variable yet deterministic, significantly deteriorating the fidelity of GDRTS. Consequently, conducting a comprehensive characterisation and thorough analysis of the time delay are essential prerequisites before the final deployment of a GDRTS setup. Furthermore, implementing advanced time delay compensation methods is crucial to ensure

Figure 13: Representation of GDRTS setups with multiple candidate RIs.

the fidelity of GDRTS, achieving accurate power signal synchronisation across the candidate RIs. This demonstration builds upon the methodologies developed in WP11-JRA2 and encompasses the following key aspects:

- (i) To characterise the time delay within the GDRTS setups across multiple candidate RIs;
- (ii) To conduct an accuracy analysis and assessment of the impact of time delay on the GDRTS accuracy along with the definition of the accuracy evaluation metrics;
- (iii) To depict the proposed machine learning-aided time delay compensation scheme and demonstrate its effectiveness in compensating for the variable yet deterministic time delay within GDRTS setups.

Hence, this demonstration serves a dual purpose: evaluating the services designed and developed in WP10-JRA1, such as “*Synthetic Inertia and Fast Frequency Response by Converter based Resources*”, and the services developed in WP12-JRA3, including “*Data Exchange*” and “*Network Monitoring*”. For a comprehensive overview of these services, refer to Deliverable D13.1 and Appendix A.

2.2.1 GDRTS Delay Characterisation

The time delay arising from multiple interfacing stages involving the digital processing of simulation platforms, signal conversion, and communication latency, is a key factor in determining the stability and accuracy of the GDRTS. From an application perspective, the time delay with time-varying yet deterministic attributes can be regarded as an uncertainty factor that affects the fidelity of GDRTS operation. A comprehensive understanding of time delay and its effects is crucial in minimising the risk of instabilities and inaccuracies during GDRTS experiments, allowing a more robust and accurate evaluation of geographically distributed complex energy systems and power apparatus. Moreover, a comprehensive characterisation of delays in GDRTS could significantly aid in the development of subsequent delay compensation schemes. This section is dedicated to identifying the characteristics of the delay, with a specific focus on its variability and uncertainty. Additionally, it focuses on characterising the time delay through an analytical approach in a probabilistic manner.

Figure 14: Representation of the time delay data collection across geographically distributed candidate RIs: (a) DPSL and PNDC in Scotland, (b) DPSL and ICCS across Europe.

Figure 15: Representation of the GDRTS delay between DPSL and PNDC with 100.000 delay samples.

The experimental time delay data across multiple RIs were collected by deploying Raspberry Pi devices in the DPSL at the University of Strathclyde (UoS). The aggregated time delay data was gathered by calculating the round-trip time taken for a small data packet (ping) to travel from DPSL to another candidate RI and back again. As depicted in Figure 13(a), the first candidate RI is PNDC, which is situated approximately 23.5 km away from DPSL geographically in Scotland. Another candidate RI selected for delay data collection is ICCS of the NTU of Athens in Greece, which is geographically located approximately 3.000 km away from DPSL.

To characterise and demonstrate the variability of the time delay within the GDRTS setup, the aggregated loop time delay data between the geographically distributed DPSL and PNDC labs with 100.000 delay samples over a randomly selected period was presented in Figure 15(a). It is evident that the loop time delay varies over time with non-periodic characteristics. The non-periodic variability of the time delay in GDRTS may be attributed to various factors, including signal conversion, coding and decoding of the interfacing signals, digital data communication, and the loss of User Datagram Protocol (UDP) packets, all of which are intrinsic properties of the GDRTS system. The non-periodic and time-varying time delay is a critical uncertainty factor that necessitates thorough characterisation and assessment before deploying the GDRTS experimental setup. Having a comprehensive uncertainty representation and quantification of the time delay variability is of great significance for the GDRTS design and operation.

Figure 16: Representation of the GDRTS delay between DPSL and ICCS with 100,000 delay samples.

In an effort to quantify the uncertainty of the time delay within the GDRTS setup, the statistical analysis methods were employed to process the time delay data presented in Figure 15(a). At the initial stage, the time delay data was grouped into 100 bins that are evenly distributed across the range of time delays collected within the GDRTS setup. The range of time delays spans from 12.18 ms to 13.20 ms. The relative probability ρ_i of each time delay bin i can be calculated as:

$$\rho_i = \frac{c_i}{N}, \quad (11)$$

where c_i is the cumulative number of observations for each time delay bin, and N is the total number of time delay samples. The frequency of observations for each time delay bin is represented in the histogram shown in Figure 15(b), which provides insights into the underlying numerical distribution of time delays and their frequency of occurrence. The histogram is asymmetrical and skewed to the left of the mean delay value. Furthermore, the histogram shown in Figure 15(b) is normalised by dividing the cumulative number of observations for each time delay bin by the total number of time delay samples as in (11). This normalisation allows us to illustrate the relative probability of a time delay value falling within each time delay bin, as in Figure 15(c).

The relative probability of the variable delay falling within the bin edges from 12.60 ms to 12.61 ms is the highest, reaching a value of 6.46%. On the other hand, the relative probability of the

variable delay falling within the bin edges at the lowest and greatest values of the range, i.e., from 12.18 ms to 12.19 ms and from 13.19 ms to 13.20 ms, respectively, is minimal, measuring at 0.001 % and 0.003 %, respectively. The non-periodic random delay data exhibit a nonuniform probability distribution, indicating asymmetry and in the occurrence of delays. This reveals the time-varying and nonuniform characteristics of the GDRTS time delay in a probabilistic manner, which contributes towards the assessment of the impact of the time delay variability and its associated uncertainty on the GDRTS accuracy.

To substantially unify the probability distribution characteristics of the time delay variability and quantify its associated uncertainty, the following Probability Density Function (PDF) estimation was employed:

$$\text{PDF} = \frac{\rho_i}{\omega_i}, \quad (12)$$

where ρ_i is the relative probability as in (11), and ω_i is the width of the time delay bin.

Note that the time delay within the GDRTS setup is considered as an aleatory uncertainty resulting from intrinsic fluctuations of the system. Moreover, the statistical characteristics of the GDRTS time delay are represented as a distribution of probability distributions, which indicates the relative likelihood that the bounded random time delay variable would fall within a specific range. Figure 15(d) depicts the PDF curve, which enables the calculation of the probability of the variable time delay falling within a specific range of delay values by summing up the area covered by the PDF estimation curve. The sum of the area covered by the PDF estimation curve is 1. As shown in Figure 15(d), the steep areas of the PDF estimation curve over the time delay bin from 12.60 ms to 12.61 ms indicate the most probable time delay values.

Furthermore, Figure 16(a) presents the aggregated loop time delay data collected between the DPSL and ICCS with 100.000 delay samples over a randomly selected period, exhibiting more pronounced time-varying and non-periodic behaviour compared to the data shown in Figure 15(a). This discrepancy may be attributed to the increasing geographical distance, resulting in longer data communication latency and an elevated loss of UDP packets, all of which are intrinsic properties of the GDRTS system. The statistical methods were applied to the delay data that was presented in Figure 16(a). The time delay data were grouped into 200 bins with a bin space of 0.034 ms that are evenly distributed across the range of time delays (i.e., from 57.18 ms to 63.97 ms). In Figure 16(b)-(d), it is evident that the relative probability of the variable delay falling within the bin edges from 58.339 ms to 58.373 ms is the highest, reaching a value of 4.98 %. This is followed by two slightly lower probabilities for the variable delay falling within the bin edges from 57.521 ms to 57.555 ms and from 59.464 ms to 59.498 ms, which are 4.01 % and 3.38 %, respectively. This observation reveals that the data displays nonuniform and asymmetrical probabilistic distribution, characterised by multimodal distribution patterns. As shown in these multimodal distributions, the delays are centred around multiple delay values rather than a single central tendency as in Figure 15(b)-(d). The presence of multiple modes indicates varying degrees of delay occurrences, contributing to more significant complexity and variability observed in the delay data.

In summary, based on the above statistical analysis and representation, it is evident that the GDRTS time delay exhibits time-varying and non-periodic behaviour, displaying nonuniform and asymmetrical probabilistic distribution characteristics. Moreover, the existence of nonuniform, asymmetrical, and multimodal probabilistic distribution characteristics introduces intrinsic randomness and uncertainty into the GDRTS system, making it challenging to predict delay occurrences or compensate for them with certainty or in a probabilistic manner. Consequently,

it poses significant challenges for a robust and accurate operation of GDRTS across geographically distributed RIs over long distances.

2.2.2 GDRTS System Modelling and Accuracy Assessment

As shown in Figure 13, GDRTS setup combines geographically distributed candidate laboratories with real-time emulated systems into a closed-loop testing configuration that mimics the original Sol in one single simulation configuration. Correspondingly, Figure 17 illustrates the equivalent diagram of the GDRTS setup comprising two interconnected System 1 (S_1) and System 2 (S_2), which are expressed in the form of a lumped voltage divider topology with two series-connected Thévenin equivalent circuits. System $S_1(s)$ consists of an equivalent voltage source V_s in series with an equivalent impedance Z_1 (i.e., $R_1 + sL_1$) of the System S_1 and system S_2 comprises one equivalent impedance Z_2 (i.e., $R_2 + sL_2$). As illustrated in Figure 17, a signal conversion, signal processing, and data communication-based interface bridges these two systems, thereby closing the simulation loop.

Figure 17: Representation of the equivalent model of GDRTS setup.

The coupling of Systems S_1 and S_2 that are split from Sol and geographically distributed across different RIs is subjected to the interface algorithms being adopted. Among the interface algorithms presented in (Ren, Steurer, & Baldwin, 2008), Ideal Transformer Model (ITM) interface is the most extensively utilised as a result of its ease of implementation and relatively high and acceptable stability and accuracy performance. In this case study, the Voltage Type-Ideal Transformer Model (V-ITM) interface is employed to define the power transmission and synchronisation manner within the GDRTS setup. As shown in Figure 17, the V-ITM interface is configured as a controllable voltage source in System S_2 that amplifies the voltage signal measure at the coupling point in System S_1 , while the current response from System S_2 is fed back to System S_1 by means of a controlled current source. By doing so, the dynamics in both systems are replicated to each other and the simulation loop is interconnected.

From the system modelling point of view, the GDRTS system is represented in the form of a SISO closed-loop system and the respective equivalent block diagram with all key components and interface signals are presented in Figure 18. The open-loop transfer function of this GDRTS closed-loop system is represented as,

$$T_O(s) = \underbrace{T_{FF1}(s) T_{FF2}(s) e^{-sT_{ff}}}_{T_{FF}(s)} \underbrace{T_{FB1}(s) T_{FB2}(s) e^{-sT_{fb}}}_{T_{FB}(s)} \frac{Z_1(s)}{Z_2(s)}, \quad (13)$$

Figure 18: Equivalent block diagram of the simulation setup in a SISO representation manner.

where $Z_1(s)$ and $Z_2(s)$ are the equivalent impedance of the Systems S_1 and S_2 , respectively. $T_{FF}(s)$ is the transfer function of the interface in the feed-forward path comprising the transfer functions of signal conversion and processing units $T_{FF1}(s)$, data communication unit $T_{FF2}(s)$, and the aggregated time delay τ_{ff} in the feed-forward path. $T_{FB}(s)$ represents the transfer function of the interface in the feedback path consisting of the transfer functions of signal conversion and processing units $T_{FB1}(s)$, data communication unit $T_{FB2}(s)$, and the aggregated time delay τ_{fb} in the feedback path. The aggregated time delay in GDRTS closed-loop is given by,

$$\tau = \tau_{ff} + \tau_{fb}. \quad (14)$$

The open-loop transfer function (11) is further expressed as:

$$T_O(s) = \underbrace{T_{FF1}(s)T_{FF2}(s)T_{FF3}(s)T_{FF4}(s)}_{T_O^*(s)} e^{-s\tau} \frac{Z_1(s)}{Z_2(s)}, \quad (15)$$

where $T_O^*(s)$ is the delay-free part of the GDRTS interface.

To assess the accuracy of GDRTS implementations, it is essential to employ metrics that support comprehensive evaluations. These metrics can be categorised into two groups: those applicable for assessing the accuracy of power synchronisation between the RIs and those suitable for evaluating the faithful reproduction of interface signals at the interfacing point at different RIs. These metrics tailored for assessing GDRTS accuracy under steady-state conditions are indispensable for developing time delay compensation schemes. They are derived as (15), where apart from the intrinsic equivalent impedance of the RIs, the system's accuracy primarily depends on the delay-free interface $T_O^*(s)$ and aggregated time delay τ . Being proportional to the frequency of the input power signal, the phase shift stemming from the aggregated time delay and the non-unity magnitude characteristic of the interface distorts the phase relationship between the voltage and current at the interfacing point at different RIs. Consequently, this leads to deteriorated Power Factor (PF) angle and inaccurate power synchronisation between different RIs, as demonstrated by the fact that an ideal case made by the geographically distributed PHIL system presents unity magnitude and zero phase lag over signal transmission, the apparent power transferred between the System 1 (S_1) and System 2 (S_2) over a certain frequency ω_k are:

$$\begin{cases} S_1 = |V_1 I_1| \angle \theta_1 = P_1 + jQ_1 \\ S_2 = |V_2 I_2| \angle \theta_2 = P_2 + jQ_2 \end{cases}, \quad (16)$$

where θ_1 is the PF angle at System 1 (i.e., $\angle V_1 - \angle I_1$), θ_2 is the PF angle at System 2 (i.e., $\angle V_2 - \angle I_2$). with the ideal GDRTS interface, $\theta_1 = \theta_2$ and $S_1 = S_2$.

In reality, for an actual GDRTS interface with a variety of interfacing components as presented in Section Figure 17, it has negative phase characteristics over a certain frequency ω_k . Note that since the phase lag stemming from the delay-free interface is significantly smaller than the millisecond-scale time delay in Section 2.2.1, it is assumed to be negligible. The actual voltage \hat{V}_2 and current \hat{I}_2 at System 2 are:

$$\begin{cases} \hat{V}_2(\omega_k) = e^{-j\omega_k\tau_{ff}} \hat{V}_1(\omega_k) = |\hat{V}_1(\omega_k)| \angle \alpha, & \alpha = \angle \hat{V}_1 - \angle \hat{V}_2 = -\omega_k\tau_{ff} \\ \hat{I}_2(\omega_k) = e^{j\omega_k\tau_{fb}} \hat{I}_1(\omega_k) = |\hat{I}_1(\omega_k)| \angle \beta, & \beta = \angle \hat{I}_1 - \angle \hat{I}_2 = \omega_k\tau_{fb} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Using φ to represent the phase lag introduced by the loop time delay, which is given by,

$$\angle \varphi = \alpha - \beta = -\omega_k(\tau_{ff} + \tau_{fb}). \quad (18)$$

Using (17) and (18), the power factor angles $\hat{\theta}_1 = \angle \hat{V}_1 - \angle \hat{I}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2 = \angle \hat{V}_2 - \angle \hat{I}_2$ can be further expressed as:

$$\hat{\theta}_2 = \hat{\theta}_1 + \varphi. \quad (19)$$

The apparent power at the System 1 (S_1) and System 2 (S_2) are expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} \hat{S}_1 = |\hat{V}_1 \hat{I}_1| \angle \hat{\theta}_1 = \hat{P}_1 + j\hat{Q}_1 \\ \hat{S}_2 = |\hat{V}_2 \hat{I}_2| \angle \hat{\theta}_2 = \hat{P}_2 + j\hat{Q}_2 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

Substituting (19) into (20), the active and reactive power at the System 2 (S_2) can be further expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} \hat{P}_2 = \hat{P}_1 \cos \varphi - \hat{Q}_1 \sin \varphi \\ \hat{Q}_2 = \hat{Q}_1 \cos \varphi + \hat{P}_1 \sin \varphi \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

Owing to the phase lag φ introduced by the aggregated loop time delay, the actual power transfer of GDRTS setup is not consistent with that given in (16). Moreover, the phase lag φ causes the active power at System 2 to be coupled with both the active and reactive power at System 1. Accordingly, the following accuracy metrics developed in (Feng et al., 2021) are adopted to assess the power synchronisation between System 1 (S_1) and System 2 (S_2):

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Power factor tracking error } \eta_\theta = \frac{|\hat{\theta}_2 - \hat{\theta}_1|}{|\hat{\theta}_1|} \\ \text{Active power tracking error } \eta_P = \frac{|\hat{P}_2 - \hat{P}_1|}{|\hat{P}_1|} \\ \text{Reactive power tracking error } \eta_Q = \frac{|\hat{Q}_2 - \hat{Q}_1|}{|\hat{Q}_1|} \end{array} \right. \quad (22)$$

On the other hand, the power signal tracking error metrics are utilised to quantitatively assess the power signal distortion and signal phase shift between System 1 (S_1) and System 2 (S_2) at

steady-state. The power signal tracking error metrics are given by,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{RMS voltage tracking error} \quad \eta_V = \frac{|\hat{V}_2 - \hat{V}_1|}{|\hat{V}_1|} \\ \text{RMS current tracking error} \quad \eta_I = \frac{|\hat{I}_2 - \hat{I}_1|}{|\hat{I}_1|} \\ \text{Voltage angle tracking error} \quad \eta_{\theta_V} = \frac{|\hat{\theta}_{V_1} - \hat{\theta}_{V_2}|}{|\hat{\theta}_{V_1}|} \\ \text{Current angle tracking error} \quad \eta_{\theta_I} = \frac{|\hat{\theta}_{I_2} - \hat{\theta}_{I_1}|}{|\hat{\theta}_{I_2}|} \end{array} \right. \quad (23)$$

These accuracy metrics are crucial for GDRTS accuracy assessment and will be further leveraged for the delay compensation schemes deviation and validation in the following sections.

2.2.3 Principles of Deep Reinforcement Learning Aided Time Delay Compensation in GDRTS Setup

As analysed in Section 2.2.2, the time delay within the GDRTS substantially undermines the synchronisation of power signals among candidate RIs, resulting in inconsistent power transfer among them, as shown in (21). This underscores the necessity for compensating for the inherent time delay to facilitate precise GDRTS simulation. As demonstrated in (Syed et al., 2020, 2022), many delay compensation techniques presuppose that the time delay is quantifiable and fixed and utilises a predetermined compensation value. However, this contradicts the findings outlined in Section 2.2.1, which reveal that the time delay within the GDRTS demonstrates time-varying and non-periodic behaviour, characterised by nonuniform and asymmetrical probabilistic distributions. Moreover, the existence of nonuniform, asymmetrical, and multimodal probabilistic distribution characteristics of the time delay introduces intrinsic randomness and uncertainty into the GDRTS system, rendering it impractical and unrealistic to compensate for it with a fixed value.

To address the drawback mentioned above of the conventional fixed-delay compensation method and facilitate the GDRTS delay compensation method with adaptivity to time-varying delays, a data-driven DRL aided delay compensation method was developed in this demonstration. Figure 19 illustrates the concept of the DRL aided time delay compensation method within the GDRTS setup. The DRL unit, comprising the agent along with its input (states and reward) and output (the action), was deployed in System 1 (S_1). Subsequently, the output of the agent is utilised in the time delay compensation unit to adjust the delay compensation value accordingly. The time delay compensation methods for the GDRTS and PHIL systems can be classified into two main categories: the dq-frame phase lead addition method (Syed et al., 2020, 2022) and the abc-frame signal manipulation method (Feng et al., 2021). As shown in Figure 20, the latter approach involves manipulating the power signal to be compensated by using the SDFT and introducing an additional phase lead before the signal reconstruction process. This delay compensation method was employed in this demonstration and its phase compensation value is updated according to the output of the DRL agent.

In the context of DRL block, as depicted in Figure 21(a), it can be mathematically formulated as MDP, which consists of an agent and environment (i.e., the system to be optimised). The interaction between an agent and its environment occurs through the exchange of signals between them. During each time step, the environment presents specific states, which the agent perceives to make decisions and take actions, thereby transitioning from one state to another.

Figure 19: Representation of the equivalent model of GDRTS setup with DRL aided delay compensation.

Simultaneously, at each time step, the agent receives a reward from the environment based on the action it takes and the resulting state transition. The reward serves as feedback on the desirability of actions taken by the agent within a given state of the environment. In essence, the agent learns to make sequential decisions by interacting with an environment, aiming to learn a policy that selects the optimal actions to maximise cumulative rewards.

As analysed in (21), the power signal phase lag arising from the time delay leads to the power mismatch between the power measure across candidate RIs. These are the theoretical conditions. These theoretical conditions serve as the basis for designing DRL. Accordingly, combined with the working principle of the MDP, as shown in Figure 21(b), the MDP implementation of the DRL aided delay compensation in GDRTS setup is summarised as follows,

1. **States:** The active power and reactive power measurement at both systems, along with the phase angle (θ_{v_1}) of the voltage signal to be sent from System 1 (S_1) to System 2 (S_2), and the phase angle (θ_{i_1}) of the current signal to be injected into System 1 (S_1) are chosen as states within the environment, namely the GDRTS setup.
2. **Reward:** As analysed in (21), the time delay undermines accuracy by introducing phase lag, resulting in a power mismatch. The power errors between P_1 and P_2 , Q_1 and Q_2 and the angle error between (θ_{i_1}) and (S_1) are chosen as the input to the reward function as they directly reveal the extent to which the time delay is compensated.
3. **Action:** After the decision made by the agent, the action taken by the agent is the addition of a phase angle θ_{comp} to be implemented in the SDFT based delay compensation.
4. **DRL learning algorithms:** Initially, the DDPG algorithm, characterised as a model-free, online, off-policy reinforcement learning method, was utilised to determine the optimal phase angle θ_{comp} for the SDFT based delay compensation. Acting as an actor-critic reinforcement learning agent, a DDPG agent endeavours to find an optimal policy that maximises the desired cumulative reward. Furthermore, to equip the DDPG agent with adaptivity to the time-varying delay, the LSTM algorithm, a type of neural network designed to retain core information over long sequences of the time delay data, thereby allowing it to capture long-range dependencies of the delay data, was integrated in series with the DDPG agent. The proposed LSTM-DDPG DRL learning algorithm was employed to train the sequential time delay data, forming an agent capable of adjusting the phase angle θ_{comp} in response to the variability of the time delay. Note that the rationale behind combining these two algorithms will be elucidated and demonstrated in the subsequent sections.

Figure 20: The block diagram of the SDFT-based time delay compensation.

Figure 21: (a) Representation of MDP, (b) representation of the MDP implementation of the DRL aided delay compensation in GDRTS setup.

2.2.4 Demonstration of Deep Reinforcement Learning Aided Time Delay Compensation in GDRTS Setup

This section is dedicated to demonstrating the applicability of the proposed LSTM-DDPG DRL aided time delay compensation method. The DRL model was trained by using the delay data collected between geographically distributed DPSL and PNDC, as illustrated in Figure 15. To provide a proof-of-concept demonstration and enable a direct comparison between the holistic system of interest and the corresponding GDRTS, we employed a voltage divider with resistive impedance circuit, as shown in Figure 19, to train the model. An equivalent voltage source V_s ($400V_{RMS}$) and a resistive grid impedance R_1 (1Ω) are employed to emulate a low-voltage grid within the System (S_1) with a resistive load R_2 (0.5Ω) in the System (S_2). The parameters of the SDFT and DRL training algorithm are tabulated in Table 1. The effectiveness of the proposed time delay compensation method was verified by assessing the power tracking performance and power signal synchronisation accuracy in both System (S_1) and System (S_2), as defined in (22) and (23). In addition, the angular information of voltage (V_1) and current (I_1) in the System (S_1), along with their error, was leveraged to validate the effectiveness of the proposed time delay compensation method.

In DRL, the episode reward, which represents the cumulative total of rewards acquired by an agent during a single episode of interaction with the environment in a reinforcement learning task, stands as a pivotal metric for evaluating the agent’s performance throughout the episode. As shown in Table 1, assuming the agent was well-trained, the cumulative reward of an episode

Table 1: Parameters of the SDFT delay compensation unit and the DRL training algorithm

System	Symbol	Description	Unit	Value
SDFT	r	Damping factor	---	0.995
	N	SDFT window size	---	400
	f_s	Sampling frequency	kHz	20
	f_0	Fundamental frequency	Hz	50
	k	Order of the complex resonator	---	[1:1:N]
DRL	T_{sDRL}	Sampling time	ms	150
	---	LSTM layer size	---	10
	---	LSTM sequence length	---	20
	---	Number of observations	---	10
	---	Maximum number of steps per episode	---	100
	---	DDPG discount factor	---	0.99
	---	DDPG actor learning rate	---	2×10^{-3}
	---	DDPG critic learning rate	---	5×10^{-3}
	---	DDPG target smooth factor	---	1×10^{-3}
	---	DDPG noise standard deviation	---	0.2582
---	DDPG noise standard deviation decay rate	---	1×10^{-5}	

Figure 22: Episode reward for agent (DDPG trained for 6.30 ms).

was computed by aggregating the individual rewards from error signals (i.e., $P_e(k)$, $Q_e(k)$, $\theta_e(k)$) as depicted in Figure 21(b), reaching its maximum value. Since the weight of the reward function was set at 5% over 100 steps per episode, the maximum reward for each error signal is 5. Consequently, the maximum cumulative reward is 15.

Scenario 1: Assessment of the DDPG agent that was trained for fixed delay when GDRTS setup has fixed delay

Initially, the DDPG algorithm was utilised to train the DRL when the GDRTS system witnessed a fixed delay, specifically the mean value (i.e., 12.62 ms) of the delay data collected between DPSL and PNDC. Figure 22 demonstrates the episode reward for the agent trained by using DDPG algorithm under such a GDRTS setup. Since the episode reward in DRL reflects the immediate feedback provided to the agent based on its actions, it is apparent from Figure 22 that the DRL learning process progresses towards optimal behaviour as the episode reward increases and eventually reaches its maximum cumulative reward (i.e., 15). The agent with maximum cumulative reward is further downloaded and implemented in the GDRTS system to validate its effectiveness in compensating for the time delay.

The behaviours of the power signals in both systems, as well as the voltage and current signals in System (S_1), are demonstrated in Figure 23. The proposed DRL time delay compensation scheme was activated at $t = 2s$. Before enabling the delay compensation, as shown in

Figure 23: Power and power signal performance of the agent (DDPG trained for 6.30 ms) aided GDRTS setup under fixed one-way delay (6.30 ms).

Table 2: Power metrics and power signal angular error metrics for scenario 1.

Time Period (s)	P_1 (kW)	P_2 (kW)	P_e (kW)	η_P	Q_1 (kVar)	Q_2 (kVar)	Q_e (kVar)	θ_e (rad)
[0 2]	-153.926	251.141	405.067	263.16 %	-198.440	0	198.440	-2.230
[2 6]	71.111	71.089	-0.022	0.031 %	-0.071	0	0.071	-0.001

Figure 23 (a) and (b), the active powers (P_1 and P_2) and reactive powers (Q_1 and Q_2) exhibit significant discrepancies compared to the Sol. Correspondingly, the active power error (P_e) and reactive power error (Q_e) were notably high, as depicted in Figure 23 (c) and (d). Additionally, the angular error between the voltage (V_1) and current (I_1) in the System (S_1) was substantial, as in Figure 23 (f) and (g). These errors outlined in Figure 23 were mitigated upon activation of the DRL-based time delay compensation. The output of the DRL unit, which was the compensation value θ_{comp} applied to SDFT, is illustrated in Figure 23 (e). The active powers (P_1 and P_2) and reactive powers (Q_1 and Q_2) became consistent with those of Sol. In addition, the angles of the voltage (V_1) and current (I_1) in the System (S_1) were aligned with each other.

Moreover, power metrics and power signal angular error metrics are presented in Table 2 to verify the functionality of the proposed time delay compensation method in a quantitative manner. Upon activation of the delay compensation, both the active and reactive power errors exhibit significant reductions, decreasing from 405.064 kW to -0.022 kW and from 198.440 kVar

Figure 24: Power and power signal performance of the agent (DDPG trained for 6.30 ms) aided GDRTS setup under multiple one-way delays (6.30 ms at 0 s to 2 s, 6.05 ms at 2 s to 4 s, 6.45 ms at 4 s to 6 s).

to 0.071 kVAr, respectively. Consequently, the active power tracking error, as defined in (22), improves remarkably, accompanied by a reduction in the angular difference θ_e between voltage (V_1) and current (I_1) in the System (S_1). In summary, the proposed DDPG based time delay compensation method effectively compensates for the delay with a fixed value within the GDRTS setup, facilitating accurate power synchronisation between two separated systems.

Scenario 2: Assessment of the DDPG agent that was trained for fixed delay when GDRTS setup has variable delay

In this scenario, the DDPG agent leveraged in scenario 1 was further evaluated when the GDRTS system witnessed variable delay. Specifically, these conditions involved the mean value (i.e., 12.62 ms) and a variation of ± 0.30 ms, based on the delay data collected between DPSL and PNDC.

Figure 24 illustrates the behaviours of the power signals in both systems, as well as the voltage and current signals in System (S_1) under variable delays. It is evident that the DDPG agent that was trained for a fixed delay of 6.30 ms successfully compensates for the delay between 0 s to 2 s when the system's one-way delay is 6.30 ms. The active powers (P_1 and P_2) and reactive powers (Q_1 and Q_2) are consistent with those of Sol, showing zero power errors. Additionally,

Table 3: Power metrics and power signal angular error metrics for scenario 2.

Time Period (s)	P_1 (kW)	P_2 (kW)	P_e (kW)	η_P	Q_1 (kVAr)	Q_2 (kVAr)	Q_e (kVAr)	θ_e (rad)
[0 2]	71.111	71.122	0.011	0.015 %	0.0186	0	-0.0186	0.0003
[2 4]	70.520	71.583	1.063	1.51 %	-12.289	0	12.289	-0.1725
[4 6]	70.934	71.252	0.318	0.45 %	6.724	0	-6.724	0.0945

the angular error between the voltage (V_1) and current (I_1) in the System (S_1) remained close to zero.

However, when variable time delays were introduced to the GDRTS system, the DDPG agent, which was initially trained for a fixed delay of 6.30 ms failed to compensate for these variable delays. This failure is obvious from Figure 24 (a)-(d), where significant disparities are observed in the active powers (P_1 and P_2) and reactive powers (Q_1 and Q_2) compared to the Sol, resulting in notable errors in active power (P_e) and reactive power (Q_e). Furthermore, there are noticeable phase discrepancies between the voltage (V_1) and current (I_1) angles, accompanied by non-negligible phase errors.

More specifically, power metrics and power signal angular error metrics are given in Table 3 to quantitatively verify the above statements. In line with Table 2, the active and reactive power errors, as well as the phase angle error between voltage (V_1) and current (I_1), are close to zero when 6.30 ms was introduced in the GDRTS setup. However, upon the application of a new one-way delay (6.05 ms), both active and reactive power errors exhibit significant increments, rising from 0.0111 kW to 1.063 kW and from -0.0186 kVAr to 12.289 kVAr, respectively. Consequently, the active power tracking error, as defined in (22), worsens remarkably, accompanied by an increase of 0.1728 rad in the angular difference θ_e between voltage (V_1) and current (I_1) in the System (S_1). Furthermore, comparing the data between 4 s to 6 s to that between 0 s to 2 s, a similar pattern of the metrics can be observed from Table 3 when a new one-way delay (6.45 ms) was introduced in the setup between 4 s to 6 s.

In summary, despite the DDPG agent, which was initially trained for a fixed delay of 6.30 ms managing to compensate for the fixed delay as in the scenario 1, it failed to compensate for variable delays. This revealed that the DDPG agent requires further improvement to enhance its adaptability to delay variability.

Scenario 3: Assessment of the DDPG agent that was trained for variable delay when GDRTS setup has variable delay

Since the DDPG agent, initially trained for a fixed delay of 6.30 ms, failed to compensate for the variable delays in scenario 2, further training was conducted with variable delays (i.e., from 6.05 ms to 6.45 ms) to evaluate its effectiveness in handling multiple variable delays. Figure 25 illustrates the episode reward for the agent trained using the DDPG algorithm with these delays. The episode reward in DRL reflects the immediate feedback provided to the agent based on its actions. Despite prolonged training, it is apparent from Figure 25 that the DRL learning process fails to progress towards optimal behaviour. Instead, the episode reward exhibits significant fluctuations rather than achieving its maximum cumulative reward (i.e., 15) as shown in Figure 22. The agent (No. 2766) with the highest cumulative reward (14.3624) was downloaded and implemented in the GDRTS system to validate its effectiveness in compensating for variable time delays.

In this scenario, the time delay varies from 6.05 ms to 6.30 ms and finally reaches 6.45 ms at different time period. Figure 26 illustrates the behaviours of the power signals in both systems, as well as the voltage and current signals in System (S_1) under these delays. It is evident that

Figure 25: Episode reward for agent (DDPG trained for 6.05 ms and 6.45 ms).

Figure 26: Power and power signal performance of the agent (DDPG trained for 6.05 ms and 6.45 ms) aided GDRTS setup under multiple delays (6.05 ms at 0 s to 2 s, 6.30 ms at 2 s to 4 s, 6.45 ms at 4 s to 6 s).

Table 4: Power metrics (in their maximum deviation from Sol value) and power signal angular error metrics (in their maximum value) for scenario 3.

Time Period (s)	P_1 (kW)	P_2 (kW)	P_e (kW)	η_P	Q_1 (kVAr)	Q_2 (kVAr)	Q_e (kVAr)	θ_e (rad)
[0 2]	71.110	71.111	0.001	0.001 %	0.412	0	-0.412	0.0058
[2 4]	69.114	73.070	-2.152	3.11 %	20.735	0	-20.735	0.2318
[4 6]	67.669	74.552	-3.587	5.09 %	26.877	0	-26.877	0.3334

the DDPG agent that was trained using variable delays (i.e., 6.05 ms and 6.45 ms) manages to compensate for the delay between 0 to 0.20s when the system's one-way delay is 6.05 ms. The active powers (P_1 and P_2) and reactive powers (Q_1 and Q_2) align with those of Sol, showing zero power errors. Additionally, the phase angles of voltage (V_1) and current (I_1) in the System (S_1) are consistent, with the angular error between the voltage (V_1) and current (I_1) in the System (S_1) remaining close to zero. As shown in Figure 26(e), the output of the agent θ_{comp} remains constant, equal to $2\pi f_0 \tau_{ff}$, where τ_{ff} equals to 6.05 ms.

However, when variable time delays 6.30 ms and 6.45 ms were introduced to the GDRTS system, the DDPG agent failed to compensate for these variable delays. This failure is obvious from Figure 26 (a)-(d), where significant disparities can be observed in the active powers (P_1 and P_2) and reactive powers (Q_1 and Q_2) with respect to the Sol, resulting in significant errors in active power (P_e) and reactive power (Q_e). Moreover, there are notable phase discrepancies between the voltage (V_1) and current (I_1) angles, accompanied by non-negligible phase errors. These errors are attributed to the fluctuation of the output of the agent θ_{comp} , as it deviates from the correct compensation value $2\pi f_0 \tau_{ff}$, where τ_{ff} equals to 6.30 ms or 6.45 ms.

In addition, power metrics and power signal angular error metrics are given in Table 4 to quantitatively support the above statements. The active and reactive power errors, as well as the phase angle error between voltage (V_1) and current (I_1), were close to zero when the GDRTS setup witnessed a 6.05 ms delay. However, upon the one-way delay variation from 6.05 ms to 6.30 ms and subsequently to 6.45 ms, both active and reactive power errors exhibit significant variation and discrepancy to those (close to zero) of Sol.

Specifically, the active power and reactive power errors (in absolute value) rose from 0.001 kW to 2.152 kW and from 0.142 kVAr to 20.735 kVAr, respectively. This directly revealed the detrimental impact of incorrect time delay compensation on the power tracing transparency between System S_1 and System S_2 . Consequently, the active power tracking error, as defined in (22), worsened remarkably, accompanied by a 0.2260 rad increase in the angular difference θ_e between voltage (V_1) and current (I_1) in the System (S_1).

Furthermore, comparing the power metrics between 4 s to 6 s with those between 2 s to 4 s, a similar pattern of the metrics can be observed from Table 4 when a new one-way delay (6.45 ms) was introduced in the setup at 4 s. However, the latter case presents notably high errors owing to the increased mismatch between the actual delay value and the output of DRL agent, which was based on an initial delay of 6.05 ms.

In summary, although the DDPG agent, which was initially trained for two variable delays (i.e., 6.05 ms and 6.45 ms), managed to compensate for 6.05 ms delay, it encountered issues when the system experienced other delays, including the 6.45 ms) used for agent training. This revealed that the DDPG algorithm fails to accurately identify the delay changes in the GDRTS setup, making it infeasible to equip the agent with adaptability to variable time delay. It further raises a new principal question: Given that the DDPG is infeasible to be adaptive for variable delays compensation, how can we modify and improve to handle delay variability effectively?

Figure 27: Episode reward for agent (DDPG+LSTM trained for multiple delays from 6.00 ms and 6.50 ms with a step of 0.05 ms).

Scenario 4: Assessment of the DDPG+LSTM agent that was trained for variable delay when GDRTS setup has variable delay

To address the limitations of the DDPG based agent in handling variable time delays, the LSTM algorithm depicted in Section 2.2.3 was further integrated with DDPG to equip the training output agent with ability to adapt to variable time delays. Figure 27 illustrates the episode reward for the agent trained using the DDPG in combination with LSTM algorithms with variable delays ranging from 6.00 ms to 6.50 ms, in 0.50 ms increments. The episode reward in DRL reflects the immediate feedback provided to the agent based on its actions. At the initial training stage, the episode reward exhibits significant fluctuations, which are attributed to the variability of time delays applied during the training process. However, after extended training, it is apparent from Figure 27 that the DRL learning process starts to progress towards optimal behaviour, with less fluctuation compared to the initial stage. The agent (No. 26084) with the highest cumulative reward of 13.5433 was downloaded and implemented in the GDRTS system to validate its effectiveness in compensating for variable time delays.

In this scenario, variable delays ranging from 6.00 ms to 6.50 ms, in 0.50 ms increment were utilised to train the DRL agent. To assess the performance of the agent, variable time delays, including those not used for agent training, were leveraged as tabulated in Table 5. Furthermore, to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed DDPG+LSTM agent and to highlight the limitations and inaccuracies of the conventional delay compensation method, which assumes a fixed delay, two case studies were performed:

- **Case 1:** GDRTS setup with fixed time delay compensation ($\theta_{\text{comp}} = 2\pi f_0 = 6.30$ ms) under multiple delays tabulated in Table 5.
- **Case 2:** DDPG+LSTM agent aided delay compensation for the GDRTS setup under multiple delays given in Table 5.

Table 5: One-way time delay (τ_{ff} and τ_{fb}) value applied for scenario 4

Time Period (s)	[0 0.30]	[0.30 0.60]	[0.60 0.90]	[0.90 1.20]	[1.20 1.50]	[1.50 1.80]
Delay Value (ms)	6.05	6.125	6.20	6.275	6.35	6.45

Figure 28: Power and power signal performance of the GDRTS setup with fixed time delay (6.30 ms) compensation under multiple delays as tabulated in Table 5.

In terms of case 1, Figure 28 illustrates the behaviours of the power signals and their associated errors in both systems, as well as the angles of the voltage and current signals in System (S_1) under the variable delays listed in Table 5. It is evident that the active powers (P_1 and P_2) and reactive powers (Q_1 and Q_2) exhibit significant discrepancies compared to the Sol, resulting in notable power errors as shown in Figure 28(c) and (d). Additionally, the phase angles of voltage (V_1) and current (I_1) in the System (S_1) are inconsistent, with greater discrepancies observed as the difference between the actual delay and the compensation value (6.30 ms) increases.

Table 6: Power metrics and power signal angular error metrics for case 1 of scenario 4.

Time Period (s)	P_1 (kW)	P_2 (kW)	P_e (kW)	η_P	Q_1 (kVAr)	Q_2 (kVAr)	Q_e (kVAr)	θ_e (rad)
[0 3]	70.622	71.502	-0.880	1.247 %	-11.185	0	-11.185	-0.157
[3 6]	70.798	71.361	-0.563	0.795 %	-8.943	0	-8.943	-0.126
[6 9]	71.033	71.173	-0.140	0.198 %	-4.469	0	-4.469	-0.063
[9 12]	71.091	71.127	-0.035	0.049 %	-2.234	0	-2.234	-0.031
[12 15]	71.093	71.126	-0.035	0.049 %	2.234	0	2.234	0.031
[15 18]	70.935	71.251	-0.316	0.446 %	6.705	0	6.705	0.094

Table 7: Power metrics and power signal angular error metrics for case 2 of scenario 4.

Time Period (s)	P_1 (kW)	P_2 (kW)	P_e (kW)	η_P	Q_1 (kVAr)	Q_2 (kVAr)	Q_e (kVAr)	θ_e (rad)
[0 3]	71.110	71.112	-0.002	0.003 %	-0.186	0	-0.186	-0.002
[3 6]	71.111	71.111	0.000	0.000 %	0.188	0	0.188	-0.002
[6 9]	71.110	71.112	-0.002	0.003 %	0.522	0	0.522	-0.001
[9 12]	71.111	71.111	0.000	0.000 %	0.505	0	0.505	-0.002
[12 15]	71.111	71.112	-0.001	0.001 %	0.331	0	0.331	0.001
[15 18]	71.110	71.112	-0.002	0.003 %	0.463	0	0.463	0.005

These can be further quantitatively assessed by using the data listed in Table 6.

During the time period from 0 s to 12 s, when the actual delay is smaller than the compensation value (6.30 ms), both active power and reactive power errors decrease as the actual delay increases and the difference between the actual delay and the compensation value decreases. Specifically, the active power error decreases from -0.880 kW to -0.035 kW, and the reactive power error decreases from -11.185 kVAr to -2.234 kVAr. This was accompanied by a reduction in the angular difference θ_e between voltage (V_1) and current (I_1) in the System (S_1), decreasing from -0.157 rad to -0.331 rad. However, once the actual delay is greater than the compensation value (6.30 ms), these power errors increase as the difference between the actual delay and the compensation value grows. These revealed that the conventional delay method, which assumes a fixed time delay compensation, suffers from remarkable inaccuracy when applied to GDRTS system with variable delays.

Regarding case 2, the acGDRTS system delay compensation was based on the agent trained using the DDPG+LSTM algorithms, with variable delays ranging from 6.00 ms to 6.50 ms in 0.50 ms increments. Figure 29 illustrates the behaviours of the power signals and their associated errors in both systems, as well as the angles of the voltage and current signals in System (S_1) under the variable delays listed in Table 5. Despite certain oscillations at the initial stage when the delay varies, the active powers (P_1 and P_2) and reactive powers (Q_1 and Q_2) align closely with those of the Sol, showing near-zero power errors for different delay applied to the GDRTS system, as shown in Figure 29(c) and (d). Furthermore, Figure 29(e) and (f) display the output of the DDPG+LSTM agent, which is consistent with the variable delays applied during each time period, as detailed in Table 5. Additionally, the phase angles of voltage (V_1) and current (I_1) in the System (S_1) are consistent, with the angular error between the voltage (V_1) and current (I_1) in the System (S_1) remaining close to zero, as shown in Figure 29(g) to (l).

In addition, power metrics and power signal angular error metrics are given in Table 7 to quantitatively support the above statements for case 2. During different time periods, the active power error, as well as the phase angle error between voltage (V_1) and current (I_1), were close to zero when the GDRTS setup witnessed variable delays. Owing to the variability of the delay applied during the agent training and the impact of the noise on the training output, there are certain

Figure 29: Power and power signal performance of the DDPG+LSTM agent aided GDRTS setup under multiple delays as tabulated in Table 5.

reactive power errors for each time delay at different time periods. However, compared to the reactive power errors in case 1, these errors are negligible.

Finally, Table 8 presents the power metrics errors for both case 1 and case 2. It is evident that the GDRTS system that is based on the DDPG and LSTM aided agent exhibits remarkably

Table 8: Power metrics error comparison between case 1 and case 2 of scenario 4.

Time Period (s)	Case 1 P_e (kW)	Case 2 P_e (kW)	Case 1 η_P	Case 2 η_P	Case 1 Q_e (kVAr)	Case 2 Q_e (kVAr)	Case 1 θ_e (rad)	Case 2 θ_e (rad)
[0 3]	-0.880	-0.002	1.247 %	0.003 %	-11.185	-0.186	-0.157	-0.002
[3 6]	-0.563	0.000	0.795 %	0.000 %	-8.943	0.188	-0.126	-0.002
[6 9]	-0.140	-0.002	0.198 %	0.003 %	-4.469	0.522	-0.063	-0.001
[9 12]	-0.035	0.000	0.049 %	0.000 %	-2.234	0.505	-0.031	-0.002
[12 15]	-0.035	-0.001	0.049 %	0.001 %	2.234	0.331	0.031	0.001
[15 18]	-0.316	-0.002	0.446 %	0.002 %	6.705	0.463	0.094	0.005

low power and angular errors compared to those of the GDRTS system with fixed time delay compensation. This demonstrates the effectiveness of the DDPG and LSTM aided agent in handling variable delays in GDRTS system, effectively equipping the system delay compensation with the ability to adapt to variable delays.

Figure 30: Schematic representation of the test case scenario, corresponding to a modified version of the CIGRE LV-distribution grid.

2.3 Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for Remote RI Testing

Distribution networks are evolving into “smart” systems, characterised by increasing complexity due to the integration of power electronic devices, ICT, smart meters, and more. This complexity calls for advanced control strategies to manage these networks effectively. Testing these systems comprehensively has become challenging as the number of components and stakeholders, including grid operators, device manufacturers, market participants, and regulators, continues to grow.

To address this challenge, the approach has been to distribute parts of the system among multiple RIs. However, conducting distributed experiments introduces its own set of challenges, mainly related to coordinating interactions between participants in these experiments. The aim of this demonstration is to showcase tools designed to expedite the setup and coordination of such distributed experiments.

For this purpose, an optimal CVC algorithm was chosen as a distribution management system. This algorithm manages various network devices capable of voltage regulation, either directly (e.g., OLTC) or by injecting active/reactive power (e.g., BESS and PV inverters). The management is based on solving an optimisation problem that minimises a predefined objective function, subject to linear and nonlinear constraints.

The CVC controller is initialised with essential static network data, including network topology, line and transformer admittance, nominal power of Distributed Energy Resource (DER) units, storage systems, operating limits, tap positions of OLTC, and more. During operation, it continuously receives real-time power measurements from smart meters installed on loads and DER units, as well as the SoC of storage systems and the current tap position of OLTC. Using this dynamic data, the controller formulates the optimal power flow problem, aiming to minimise voltage deviation, power losses, and tap change operations.

The evaluation focuses on assessing the ability of tools developed in the WP11-JRA2 and WP12-JRA3 for interoperability and their effectiveness in rapidly configuring and adapting distributed experiments. This assessment includes comparing the amount of lines of code required for setting up the experiment before and after implementing these tools in the demonstration.

2.3.1 Software tools

In this subsection, we give a short summary of the software tools that were used in this Demo. Figure 31 shows an example setup involving two RIs. The software tools for supporting the setup of this experiment are the *Configuration Management Tool* and the *uAPI*. They are intended to support the preparation and the execution processes, respectively.

The uAPI allows to support a wider set of protocols for internal communications in the laboratories, through an improved reuse of protocol conversion modules. To understand the main functionality of the uAPI in more detail, two distinctions have to be made regarding the communications and related protocols and tools:

- **Transport communications** constitute the interconnection among geographically distributed RIs. Because communications are established over long distances, it is desired to have best effort protocols for transport communication, e.g. IP/UDP. In the ERIGrid 2.0 project, three main tools have been implemented/improved, for providing the transport communications: VILLASnode, Joint test facility for smart energy Networks with Dis-

Figure 31: Software tools for improved setup of multi-RI experiments.

tributed Energy Resources (JaNDER) and Lablink. They are known as *Lab Coupling Tools*, as can be seen in Figure 31, or alternatively, *Transports*.

- **Internal communications:** They take place inside the RI. Normally, there is a device acting as a central hub, collecting data coming from the DRTS, controller devices and power devices. This requires most of the times interactions with a SCADA system. Several solutions can be considered for achieving interoperability among these devices: from custom software modules to internal APIs. In the ERIGrid 2.0 project, the term *RI Adapter* was introduced to denote the software modules performing conversion among several protocols for communicating devices inside the RI.

The uAPI was developed in WP12-JRA3 to enable the reuse of the RI Adapters among the laboratories of the consortium, and the community in general. The main idea is to convert all the RI's internal data to a common format, provided by a representational state transfer (REST) Application Programming Interface (API). The next requirement is that the transports support the uAPI, so that every new RI Adapter can be reused by the other transports. For example, let us assume that RI 1, which normally uses VILLASnode as transport, developed an adapter supporting Modbus, which means that messages are converted from this protocol to the uAPI. This adapter could be reused directly by any of the remaining two transports (JaNDER and Lablink), since they support the uAPI as well.

2.3.2 Multi-RI Setup

Figure 30 shows the test case scenario, which is a modified version of the CIGRE LV-distribution grid (Maniatopoulos, Lagos, Kotsampopoulos, & Hatziargyriou, 2017). The grid is intended to include a representative amount of renewable generation and BESS. To test the ability of the tools developed in the WP11-JRA2 and WP12-JRA3 for setting up multi-RI experiments, a GD-PHIL was implemented among several laboratories. Given the availability of hardware devices in these laboratories, we chose to use only PV generation and BESS. The Real Time Digital Simulator (RTDS) part was implemented in the Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen (RWTH)'s RTlab. Moreover, the CVC was implemented as a CHIL in the same laboratory. The other RIs participating in the experiment provide their SIL or PHIL implementations

Figure 32: Load and generation profiles for PV generators.

that represent a specific part of the scenario, e.g. a PV generator, residential loads or BESS. Furthermore, they connect to RWTH forming a star topology. Given the characteristics of the experiment, i.e. the CVC having a slow sampling rate (15 min) and the fact that there are no fast simulation transients, it is possible to use an *Asynchronous AC* coupling approach (Syed et al., 2022), through which the bus' Root Mean Square (RMS) voltages and system frequency are exchanged. Furthermore, we assume that the frequency does not change, then it is not necessary to send it. Therefore, the signals that need to be exchanged between the the RIs doing PHIL and the central RI are, as follows:

- To reproduce the bus voltages in the RIs implementing PHIL, the bus' RMS voltages are sent from the central RI,
- the signals required by the CVC include the active and reactive power of PV and loads, and the SoC of the batteries,
- the setpoints computed by the CVC are the reactive power of the PV, the active and reactive power of the BESS, and the position of the OLTC.

The behaviour of the loads and the renewable generation follows a predefined profile, as shown in Figure 32. The specific generation and load on each bus is obtained by multiplying these profiles by the maximum active and reactive powers, according to tables 9 and 10.

Table 9: Maximum load active and reactive powers.

Load number	Maximum Active Power (in kW)	Maximum Reactive Power (in kVAr)
1	1.5	1
2	15	10
3	6.5	4
4	1.5	1
5	6.5	4

An initial version of the simulation model for the RTDS platform was provided by National Technical University of Athens (NTUA). They supported the validation process of this scenario with the CVC. Figure 33 shows in detail the configuration of the experiment for two RIs, for the sake of a simplified illustration. All the RIs participating in the experiment are described, as follows:

- **RWTH:** This laboratory constitutes the central RI. As mentioned previously, it runs the simulation model in the RTDS platform, and the CVC in Matlab. These two modules

Figure 33: Schematic showing the implementation details of the GD-RTS setup between two RI.

Figure 34: Demo 3 deployment in Tecnia for multi-RI testing.

communicate via UDP Sockets. In this case, communications were enabled by the VILLASnode gateway. VILLASnode is a real-time capable and flexible gateway which supports multiple communication protocols. During this demo, VILLASnode was improved to support the WebRTC¹ protocol, which allows a quick setup of transport communications using well-known ports. It is ideal for Geographically Distributed (GD)-RTS experiments using protocols like UDP, which adds more overhead from the administrative point of view, since RI's normally have strict cyber-security rules and special requests for port-forwarding have to be made. This protocol resulted in a much smoother implementation of the experiments with the different partners.

- **Tecnalia (TEC):** This laboratory emulates the behaviour of the bus highlighted in orange in Figure 30. PV generation is emulated through a Power electronics converter (PV emulator + inverter), whereas loads are emulated by two active and reactive load banks. Moreover, a grid emulator is also used to recreate the AC electric network with the data provided by the remote RWTH RI. The software is deployed in several containers which control this real hardware (in grey in Figure 34). Three of them are highlighted in the figure:
 - The *sendtovillas* container is continuously reading the measures from the bays where the PV generation and the loads are connected and sends the values (P and Q) to the *VILLASnode* container by means of UDP packets. This is decoupled from the test execution.
 - The *jradero3* container is a sequencer which, once instantiated, reads the test files, setting the setpoints according to the time elapsed of the test in progress. It is also listening to UDP messages from *VILLASnode* to modify the reactive power of the PV generation, as well as to set the same voltage of the multi-RI overall system.
 - The *VILLASnode* container is a VILLASnode process with two nodes which connects the TEC RI with the RWTH RI by means of the WebRTC protocol. The configuration file establishes one path to translate webRTC messages into UDP packets to send the setpoints to the *jradero3*, and another path to translate UDP packets coming from *VILLASnode* into webRTC messages.

The accelerated tests are auto-synchronised by means of timers and the first exchanged message. Both RI share the same time scale (1:60, 60 s will be executed within 1 s), therefore, when synchronised, both remote RIs moves to the same timestep configured in the test. When TEC RI receives the first setpoint from RWTH, it serves as the starting point of the test. After this, the timers of both RIs move towards the accelerated test using the same time scale and the test execution is synchronised.

- **Technical University of Denmark (DTU):** The test configuration at the DTU SYSLAB facility includes three physical units: A 120 kV A Cinergia GE+vAC grid emulator as the grid forming coupling unit, an 80 kW, 256-step resistive load bank representing the building load and a 40 kV A Cinergia GE&EL+vAC inverter configured as a controllable power source used to simulate PV input. The original plan of using 30 kWp of actual PV capacity was dropped in favour to make the test less weather dependent, and due to frequent and time consuming triggering of the PV inverters' anti-islanding protection by strong excursions of grid voltage and frequency in the initialisation phase of the coupling experiment. As the test assumed all units to be connected to the same bus, the units were interconnected by the shortest possible path of about 35 m between the grid forming unit and the

¹<https://webrtc.org/>

load.

A spare server was chosen to host the *VILLASnode* which used a WebRTC node on the path to RWTH, and a UDP node to communicate to a custom interface script running on the same machine. This script stood for the bidirectional translation between the UDP messages and the facility internal, Remote Procedure Call (RPC)-based protocol to communicate with the distributed control nodes within the laboratory.

- **SINTEF:** The laboratory setup at SINTEF models a BESS using a real-time simulator, OPAL-RT, which includes six battery cells connected in series with a total capacity of 50 kV A. A separate Linux machine serves as the communication interface to the setup at RWTH, utilizing uAPI JaNDER transport technology for remote communication. Locally, the OPC-UA protocol is used to facilitate the communication between this interface machine and the real-time simulator. A Python script running as an OPC client on the interface machine facilitates the data exchange every 100 milliseconds. It reads active power, reactive power, and SoC measurements from the OPC server on the OPAL-RT and sends these measurements to the CVC at RWTH. Simultaneously, it fetches reference values for active power and reactive power from the CVC, the voltage at the PCC from the model running at RWTH, and sends them to the OPC server on the OPAL-RT.
- **UoS:** The DPSL lab at the University of Strathclyde simulated the behaviour of BESS to demonstrate the Battery Management System (BMS) functionality of the CVC algorithm. As highlighted in the pastel orange circle in Figure 30, the test configuration at DPSL consists of a three-phase, 30kW battery system that is coupled to the CIGRE LV-distribution grid via a grid-tie converter. The communication between RWTH and DPSL was achieved by employing the UDP packets-based *VILLASnode*. A *VILLAS* supernode was established in a high-performance machine in the UoS network, using Linux. This supernode consisted of a WebRTC node to transfer data with RWTH and another socket node for data transfer with the RTDS in UoS. RTDS used its GTNET card for data communication with the *VILLAS* supernode at UoS. To demonstrate the effectiveness of BMS, UoS received the voltage at the PCC from the model running at RWTH, as well as the active and reactive power set points, which were utilised as the command power signal to regulate the output current of the grid-tie converter. Additionally, the current SoC of the battery and the active and reactive output power of the grid-tie converter were measured and sent back to RWTH via *VILLASnode*. This setup allows the dynamic response of the BESS to feed back into the CVC, incorporating the BESS system into the closed-loop real-time simulation environment.

Table 10: Parameters of PV generators.

PV number	Nominal Apparent Power (in kvar)	Maximum Active Power (in kW)	Power Factor
1	40	30	0.8 ... 1 leading or lagging
2	20	15	0.8 ... 1 leading or lagging
3	4	3	0.8 ... 1 leading or lagging
4	20	15	0.8 ... 1 leading or lagging

2.3.3 Experimental Results

Due to organisational issues, it was not possible to schedule a joint experiment with all the involved RIs simultaneously, although successful experiments were made separately with five of them. Here, we will report results of a joint experiment with three RIs: RWTH, TEC, and DTU.

The initial experiment entails the validation of the CVC. This experiment gives the baseline against which the multi-RI experiment results are compared. The validation consists of two steps. First, the system model is executed without the CVC. This gives an extra baseline to evaluate its performance. Figure 35 shows the load voltages, which correspond to the ones already reported (Maniatopoulos et al., 2017).

Second, the validation experiment is carried out with the CVC. Figure 36 shows the load voltages with the CVC.

Figure 37 shows the results of the multi-RI experiment. Here, the main differences with the validation scenario are mainly given by the fact that one of the RIs' PV system was providing actual active and reactive power and, since the experiment was run on an accelerated way, i.e. 15 min were simulated as 15 s, the PV generation was relatively low and essentially did not change during the experiment.

Figure 35: Load voltages in the open-loop validation scenario (e.g. without CVC).

Figure 36: Load voltages in the validation scenario with the CVC.

Figure 37: Load voltages in the multi-RI scenario with the CVC.

2.3.4 Setting Up The Experiment Using the Configuration Management Tool

As the number of RI participating in the experiment grows, so does the complexity for setting it up, especially in terms of configuration. Moreover, the simulation scenario and the parameters of the experiment can change very often. For example, let us assume that a RI takes the place of another one in the experiment. In this case, the new RI could have different parameters like the units of the incoming signals. Moreover, communication parameters can also change like domain names and port numbers. As part of JRA3, the ERIGrid 2.0 project developed a CM tool to facilitate this setup process. The philosophy of this tool consists of three steps that are organised hierarchically, as shown in Figure 38. The starting point is the preparation of a centralised, global configuration file, which can be placed in a common repository. This file describes the global interconnection of the laboratories, and specifies which transport is going to be used by which RI. The second step consists in running the CM tool, which produces the local configuration files to be used by the RIs. This step could be automated by means of a Continuous Integration / Continuous Delivery (CI/CD) workflow, which triggers the CM tool every time a new version of the Global Configuration file is pushed to the common repository. Finally, the third step consists on running the Launcher tool, which translates the local configuration to the specific lab coupling tool, which in the case of Figure 38 corresponds to VILLASnode. Moreover, there is an optional step contemplating the use of a patch file with which the local configuration is extended to reflect the internal setup of the RI. This is explained in more detail in the next paragraph.

We can exemplify the use of the CM tool by referring to the simplified case of two RI, as shown in Figure 33. After applying the global CM tool, the resulting local configuration file corresponds to the one shown in code listing 1.

The transport block specifies the lab coupling tool together with its configuration properties, which in the case of VILLASnode, describes the node type which establishes the coupling to the other RI. This node is called *transport node*. There are three different transports in the ERIGrid 2.0 project: VILLASnode, JaNDER and Lablink. The last step of the CM process consists on generating the configuration of the specific transport from the local configuration file and using it for executing the coupling tool. The tool performing this last step is known as *launcher*. For the case of VILLASnode, the launcher was implemented in Python, using the Pydantic² tool for

²<https://docs.pydantic.dev/latest/>

Figure 38: Overview of the CM workflow.

Listing 1: Local configuration file for the “Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for Remote RI Testing” demonstration.

```

1  # Local RWTH mvp config
2  nodes:
3    channels:
4      incoming:
5        - { id: Ppv3in, description: "PV active power measurement", datatype: float, unit: W }
6        - { id: Qpv3in, description: "PV reactive power measurement", datatype: float, unit: Var }
7        - { id: Pl3in, description: "Load active power measurement", datatype: float, unit: W }
8        - { id: Ql3in, description: "Load reactive power measurement", datatype: float, unit: Var }
9      outgoing:
10       - { id: BUS9arms, description: "PCC voltage", datatype: float, unit: kV }
11       - { id: Qpv3in_setpoint, description: "PV reactive power setpoint", datatype: float, unit: kVar }
12
13     transport:
14       type: villas
15
16     # All following attributes are specific to the type of transport
17     # and not covered by the global config schema.
18     villas-node:
19       node-type: webrtc
20       node-format: json
21       node-session: erigrid2-demo3-tec
22       node-server: https://villas.k8s.eonerc.rwth-aachen.de/ws/signaling
23       node-wait-seconds: 120
24       resolver-result:
25         startup-sequence: 1

```

validation and for generating the VILLASnode configuration file. The process was facilitated by taking advantage of the existing Open API definition³, and using it to build the data model by means of the datamodel-code-generator tool⁴. In the first version of the launcher, the resulting configuration is patched by providing a template file as an additional input, which completes the VILLASnode configuration file. This is the most common scenario for VILLASnode, since

³<https://villas.fein-aachen.org/api/node/>

⁴<https://github.com/koxudaxi/datamodel-code-generator>

Listing 2: VILLASnode configuration file for RWTH in the “Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for Remote RI Testing” demonstration.

```

1  {
2      "uuid": "55a0cd41-7d2d-49e7-a33d-25c55a5dca90",
3      "nodes": {
4          "tec": {
5              "type": "webrtc",
6              "format": "json",
7              "session": "erigrd2-demo3-tec",
8              "server": "https://villas.k8s.eonerc.rwth-aachen.de/ws/signaling",
9              "wait_seconds": 120,
10             "in": {
11                 "signals": [
12                     {
13                         "name": "Ppv3in",
14                         "unit": "W",
15                         "type": "float"
16                     },
17                     {
18                         "name": "Qpv3in",
19                         "unit": "Var",
20                         "type": "float"
21                     },
22                     {
23                         "name": "Pl3in",
24                         "unit": "W",
25                         "type": "float"
26                     },
27                     {
28                         "name": "Ql3in",
29                         "unit": "Var",
30                         "type": "float"
31                     }
32                 ]
33             },
34             "out": {}
35         }
36     }
37 }

```

the transport messages can be directly mapped to one of the many protocols supported by this tool. The second version of the launcher will use the uAPI as the default node type to which the messages are forwarded from the transport node. This scenario is typically found in cases where there is a simulator or a device with a protocol not currently supported by VILLASnode. Figure 39 illustrates this scenario in the hypothetical case of this demonstration, with TEC using the Profibus protocol, which is not currently supported by VILLASnode. Notice that the RI adapter is independent on the transport, therefore, it can be kept if changing the transport from VILLASnode to, for instance, JaNDER, or, alternatively, the adapter could have been implemented in another RI, and reused in RWTH using VILLASnode. In this case, the launcher delegates the internal communications management to the RI adapter. The code listing 2 shows an extract of the VILLASnode configuration file produced by the launcher. It can be seen that the mapping is properly done from the local configuration file (code listing 1), and conforms to the VILLASnode configuration schema.

2.4 Multi-Energy District Flexibility

The integration of local energy systems has emerged as a practical solution to address the challenges posed by the widespread use of non-programmable RESs. In light of this, the objective of this demonstration is to assess the technical feasibility of employing power-to-heat

Figure 39: Hypothetical case of the “Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for Remote RI Testing” demonstration showing the use of the uAPI.

technology in a local multi-energy district and to evaluate its impact on both the electrical and thermal networks. By combining electric and thermal storage systems and incorporating flexible loads like heat pumps, thermal loads, and electric boilers, this demonstration aims to investigate the heating system’s potential to provide services to the electrical system, including congestion management and balancing power provision. An overview of the electrical and thermal systems can be seen in Figure 40.

This demonstration represents a significant advancement in the field because multi-energy districts are intricate systems that are challenging to replicate in laboratory environments. Furthermore, it offers a unique opportunity to conduct hardware tests by integrating resources from various RIs, creating an extended RI with more extensive capabilities than any single laboratory.

This demonstration utilises tools developed in WP11-JRA2 and WP12-JRA3 to replicate the multi-energy district by integrating equipment across multiple RIs. The interchange of data among these RIs is facilitated by the tools developed in WP11-JRA2 and managed through services provided by WP12-JRA3. Therefore, this demonstration serves a dual purpose: evaluating the services designed and developed in WP11-JRA2, such as “Accelerating time-to-experiment for remote RI coupling,” and the services developed in WP12-JRA3, including “Data Exchange,” “Network Monitoring,” and “Time-synchronisation”, and assessing the potential of employing power-to-heat technology in a local multi-energy district to provide services to the

Figure 40: Schematic representation of the “Multi-Energy District Flexibility” demonstration, with the electrical and thermal systems highlighted by blue and red dashed boxes, respectively.

electrical system. For a comprehensive overview of these services, refer to Deliverable D13.1 and Appendix A.

2.4.1 Experimental Results

In the context of this investigation, the provision of critical services to the electrical grid is explored, with a particular emphasis on congestion management — including the constraints associated with electrical import and export — and the provision of regulating power. The focal point of this demonstration is the assessment of a Centralised Supervisory Controller (CSC) within a geographically distributed local multi-energy system. This analysis is pivotal in understanding the operational dynamics of system components that are interconnected across various regions.

Figure 41: Schematic representation of the CIGRE LV-distribution benchmark grid.

The experimental setup encompasses a tripartite system: an electrical grid with energy sources, a thermal network, and an advanced control system, all graphically represented in Figure 40.

The *thermal infrastructure* (red dashed box) is divided into two systems. The first is a District Heating Network (DHN) located in Denmark at DTU, interfaced with a CHP unit based in Italy at Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico (RSE), connected through an electrical coupling unit. The second system consists of a thermal load (L1) powered by an EHP, both situated in Greece at the Center For Renewable Energy Sources (CRES). The *electrical infrastructure* (blue dashed box) includes a distribution grid and a few controllable units. The distribution grid adopts the CI-GRE LV-distribution benchmark (Maniatopoulos et al., 2017), characterised by a 0.4 kV, 50 Hz low-voltage system with resources working as controllable current sources, allowing precise control over active (P) and reactive power (Q) through the calculation of current magnitude and phase relative to the bus voltage. The schematic representation of this network is detailed in Figure 41. This network is emulated through an RTDS real-time simulator located in the Netherlands at the Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), with two physically different nodes virtually interfaced in a GDS setup. To these nodes, PCC2 and PCC4, are connected the simulated BESS of SINTEF, and the CHP with the EHP, respectively. The *control system* delves with accurately determining setpoints for these controllable entities to ensure the delivery of required services.

Figure 42: Schematic representation of the district heating network at DTU, with approximate measurement locations marked.

Regarding the hardware setup of the experiment, it includes several key components. The EHP (CRES) has nominal power 16 kW and capacity 18 kV A, with controllable variables including its operating state (on/off). Various measurements are recorded, such as active, reactive, and apparent power, energy consumption, voltage, frequency, and indoor temperature at multiple points. Interfacing with other RIs involves data collection via an eWon 4001 datalogger and control through a Raspberry Pi 4 Model B.

The DHN (DTU) consists of two 440 m long double pipes running between two buildings (Figure 42). Building 1 contains a controllable electrical heat source and a controllable heat consumer. The only role of building 2 is that of a thermal substation interconnecting the two pipes such that the source and sink in building 1 are separated by 880 m of pipe. The heat source consists of a stack of nine electrical flow heaters with a total power of each 22.5 kW, feeding into a 200 L accumulator tank. Due to the size mismatch between the output ranges of the CHP plant at RSE (from 46 kW to 81 kW) and the input range of the heat source at DTU (0 kW to 22.5 kW), a linear mapping function offsets and scales the thermal power setpoints received through the coupling interface such that the entire controllable range of the CHP plant is mapped to the

Table 11: Description of the signals exchanged among RIs, including their symbols and operational ranges.

Symbol	Description	Unit	Min Value	Max Value
P_{elSIN}	Active power from Grid Forming Converter (SINTEF)	kW	-40	40
Q_{elSIN}	Reactive power from Grid Forming Converter (SINTEF)	kVAr	-5	5
V_{SIN}	Voltage from Grid Forming Converter (SINTEF) to Distribution Grid (TUD)	V	150	400
P_{elSIN}^{ref}	Active power from Controller to ESS (SINTEF)	kW	-40	40
Q_{elSIN}^{ref}	Reactive power from Controller to ESS (SINTEF)	kVAr	-5	5
SoC	State-of-charge BESS	%	0	100
V_{SIN}^{ref}	Voltage ref from Distribution Grid (TUD) to Grid Forming Converter (SINTEF)	V	150	400
f_{SIN}^{ref}	Frequency ref from Distribution Grid (TUD) to Grid Forming Converter (SINTEF)	Hz	48	52
P_{elRSE}	Active power from Grid Forming Converter (RSE) to Distribution Grid (TUD)	kW	-100	100
Q_{elRSE}	Reactive power from Grid Forming Converter (RSE) to Distribution Grid (TUD)	kVAr	-50	50
V_{RSE}^{ref}	Voltage ref from Distribution Grid (TUD) to Grid Forming Converter (RSE)	V	150	400
f_{RSE}^{ref}	Frequency ref from Distribution Grid (TUD) to Grid Forming Converter (RSE)	Hz	48	52
on/off	ON/OFF EHP (CRES)	boolean	0	1
T_{1CRES}	Thermal measurement Heat Distribution (CRES)	°C	12	28
T_{2CRES}	Thermal measurement Heat Distribution (CRES)	°C	12	28
T_{3CRES}	Thermal measurement Heat Distribution (CRES)	°C	12	28
P_{thCRES}	Active power of Heat Pump (CRES)	kW	0	30
T_{1DTU}	Temperature at heat source buffer tank (DTU)	°C	0	100
\dot{m}_{DTU}	Mass flow through heat distribution feeder (DTU)	l/min	0	1000
$T_{fwd1DTU}$	Forward temperature at start of heat distribution feeder (DTU)	°C	0	100
$T_{ret1DTU}$	Return temperature at start of heat distribution feeder (DTU)	°C	0	100
$T_{fwd2DTU}$	Forward temperature at midpoint of heat distribution feeder (DTU)	°C	0	100
$T_{ret2DTU}$	Return temperature at midpoint of heat distribution feeder (DTU)	°C	0	100
$T_{fwd3DTU}$	Forward temperature at heat load / end of feeder (DTU)	°C	0	100
$T_{ret3DTU}$	Return temperature at heat load / end of feeder (DTU)	°C	0	100
P_{thDTU}	Power dissipated by heat load (DTU)	kW	0	50
\dot{P}_{thDTU}	Heat charged by heat source into buffer tank (DTU)	kW	0	25
P_{thCHP}	Heat output of RSE CHP plant (=setpoint to DTU heat source)	kW	46	81
P_{elCHP}	Active power setpoint RSE CHP	kW	25	50
f_{RSE}	Frequency from Grid Forming Converter (RSE)	Hz	48	52
V_{RSE}	Voltage from Grid Forming Converter (RSE)	V	150	400
P_{elSIN}	Active power measured as output from the CHP (RSE)	kW	0	50
Q_{elSIN}	Reactive power measured as output from the CHP (RSE)	kVAr	-25	25
P_{elCHP}	Active power measured as output from the EHP emulator (RSE)	kW	-20	20
Q_{elCHP}	Reactive power measured as output from the EHP emulator (RSE)	kVAr	-10	10

entire controllable range of the heat source.

In order to follow the dynamic response of the DHN circuit, temperature measurements are positioned at the output of the heat source, in six places along the forward line and at the input of the heat consumer.

The three-phase distribution grid (TUD) operates at 0.4 kV, 50 Hz and supplies five loads (see Figure 41). The BESS managed by SINTEF includes a converter and a power amplifier, along with measurement points including SoC and instantaneous power. Lastly, the CHP (RSE) plant utilises a natural gas internal combustion engine, bidirectional converters, and power amplifiers within a three-phase low-voltage grid setup. Further details regarding the hardware setup, refer to Deliverable D13.1, specifically in “Appendix 4: Demonstration 4 HTD”.

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed experimental setup and demonstrate the feasibility of providing ancillary services through power-to-heat strategies in a local multi-energy district, a sector-coupling experimental demonstration inspired by (Widl, Wild, Heussen, Rikos, & Hoang, 2022) was conducted.

The performed experiments demonstrated the impact of providing flexibility services on both the electrical and thermal networks. The amount of flexibility requested by the system operator is achieved through the control of electric and thermal units, such as storage systems,

Figure 43: Reference voltage sent from the distribution grid (TUD) to the grid forming converters (SINTEF and RSE), along with the active power generated by the BESS and CHP and enable signals of the EHP in the overvoltage scenario.

heat pumps, thermal loads, and electric boilers. The distributed laboratory setup, as shown in Figure 40, utilises the uAPI for data exchange. Given the “slower” dynamics typical of electro-thermal experiments, which operate on the scale of seconds, the data-exchange rate is set between 1 Hz to 2 Hz. Two distinct working scenarios were delineated:

- **Case 1 – Overvoltage Scenario:** this scenario addresses an overvoltage condition triggered by high PV generation, either PV1 and PV3 located at PCC4 and PCC3, respectively, as depicted in Figure 41. This condition is coupled with low electricity demand. It is noteworthy that the DHN does not influence the outcomes in this scenario.
- **Case 2 – Undervoltage Scenario:** this scenario examines an undervoltage condition resulting from reduced or nonexistent PV generation and elevated electricity demand. It mirrors the overvoltage scenario (Case 1) with the critical distinction of employing negative threshold values for the operational parameters of the units. This condition necessitates the engagement of both the CHP unit and thermal storage to ensure grid stability.

This comprehensive case study aims to shed light on the operational efficacy of a CSC within a distributed multi-energy framework, highlighting its capacity to manage grid congestions and provide regulating power under a spectrum of operational conditions.

Figure 43 illustrates the outcomes of the overvoltage scenario aimed at addressing high PV generation coupled with low electricity consumption, leading to an overvoltage condition. To

Figure 44: Reference and actual active power profiles at the SINTEF facility, along with the SoC of the BESS, during the overvoltage scenario experiment. Additionally, reactive power and frequency data are included.

prepare for this test, TUD developed profiles for the PVs and simulated loads⁵, inducing a significant voltage rise at the nodes connected to SINTEF (V_{SIN}^{ref}) and RSE (V_{RSE}^{ref}). During the test, SINTEF and RSE, integrated into the simulation model (see Figure 40), active power consumption (P_{elSIN} and P_{elRSE}) to mitigate voltage deviations. SINTEF employed a simplified control approach, adjusting the active power setpoint of the battery in a stepwise manner, as depicted in the lower left plot of Figure 43. For instance, significant power consumption was activated if the voltage rise exceeded 5% and deactivated if it dropped below 0%, ensuring stability during the test. Similarly, RSE employed the same hysteresis approach to control the electricity consumption of CRES' heat pump, reducing the voltage rise at the corresponding node, as shown in the plots on the right side of Figure 43. It is important to note that the 5% threshold is indicative and may vary based on the simulated profiles, highlighting the necessity for accurate estimations via offline simulations. Furthermore, in this scenario, where an increase in electric load is necessary, neither the thermal power of the combined heat and power (CHP) unit nor the thermal capacity of the heat network (DTU) can be utilised to mitigate the overvoltage condition.

In this context, RSE could still communicate the thermal (P_{thCHP}) setpoint value to DTU, but it would need to be set to zero as it does not play any role. Whereas, Figure 44 illustrates the reference (P_{elSIN}^{ref}) and actual (P_{elSIN}) active power profiles, as well as the relative increase in the

⁵The PVs and simulated loads profiles are not included here for brevity and as they are not crucial to the purpose of the case study which primarily focuses on showcasing the viability of deployment of the JaNDER software middleware and uAPI.

Figure 45: Reference voltage sent from the distribution grid (TUD) to the converters (SINTEF and RSE), along with the active power generated by the BESS and CHP, and the enable signals of the EHP, in the undervoltage scenario.

SoC of the BESS, at the SINTEF facility. Additionally, it shows the reactive power profiles of SINTEF (Q_{elSIN}) and RSE (Q_{elRSE}), along with the reference frequencies (f_{SIN}^{ref} and f_{RSE}^{ref}).

This scenario allowed for evaluating and assessing the WP11-JRA2 and WP12-JRA3 services, such as “Accelerating time-to-experiment for remote RI coupling”, “Data Exchange”, “Network Monitoring” and “Time-synchronisation”.

The control strategy was simplified, primarily focusing on adjusting active power without considering other parameters like temperatures. If any anomalies arise during the experiments, involved partners could locally override setpoints and deactivate equipment. While both experiments could be combined into one, conducting them separately was more time-efficient, considering the real-time nature of the tests.

Figure 45 presents the outcomes in the electrical domain of the undervoltage scenario, where the voltage at the coupling points of SINTEF and RSE suddenly drops below the reference value (240 V) due to low or zero PV generation or high consumption in the grid (see Figure 41). The procedure for this scenario parallels that of the overvoltage scenario, employing a negative threshold value of -5% for activation and 0% for deactivation of units. Initially, the CRES EHP operates to ensure its deactivation during the experiment, as shown in the lower right corner of Figure 45. Hence, the scenario necessitates additional generation by the CHP, requiring the utilisation of both the CHP of RSE and the thermal network (DTU).

To restore the voltage to the reference value (or close to it), RSE generated active power (P_{elRSE})

Figure 46: Power and SoC of the BESS at SINTEF, alongside the temperature of the heat source buffer tank, and the power of heat sent to the buffer, in the undervoltage scenario.

by disabling the EHP ($P_{th_{CRES}}$ goes to zero) and activating the CHP, while the BESS stopped charging (P_{elSIN} goes to zero). This recovery process, depicted in Figure 47, occurs within minutes due to the rapid dynamics involved. Notably, the increase in voltage is not directly correlated with active power but instead requires reactive power (Q_{elSIN} and Q_{elRSE}), as evident in the plots (see Figure 47). The system utilises thermal energy to provide services, with insufficient generation of reactive power resulting in the need to generate active power. This supports the fault ride-through capability, enabling the RIs to remain connected despite voltage fluctuations and provide voltage support and thermal heating services. Figure 46 demonstrates a decrease in load due to the BESS stopping its charging, illustrating the impact of the electrical grid on the thermal network. The battery was maintained at 50 % capacity, as observed in the lower left corner of Figure 46.

The undervoltage scenario also facilitated the testing and evaluation of the services outlined in WP12-JRA3, including “Accelerating time-to-experiment for remote RI coupling,” “Data Exchange,” “Network Monitoring,” and “Time-synchronisation.” These evaluations assessed the technical feasibility of employing power-to-heat technology in a local multi-energy district and the impact on both the electrical and thermal networks. In conclusion, the conducted experiments in both scenarios demonstrated the adaptability and robustness of the WP11-JRA2 and WP13-JRA3 services to address the challenges posed by the widespread use of non-programmable RESs.

The response of the thermal system is depicted in Figure 48. The bottom graph shows the output of the controllable heat source over the period of three hours within which both experiments were conducted. As mentioned above, the heat source directly tracks the heat output

Figure 47: Reference voltage, reactive power, and reference frequencies at the SINTEF and RSE facilities, with a zoomed-in view showing the evolution of the reference voltage in the undervoltage scenario.

of the remote CHP plant, but with an offset and a scaling factor applied to match the two units' controllable ranges, and with limited resolution of 2.5 kW due to the size of the individual load steps.

The dashed vertical line across both graphs marks the end of the coupling experiment. After this point, no further data is exchanged between RI and the heat source is switched off. All dynamic processes after this point are exclusively happening in the heat system. This highlights one of the challenges of multi-domain experiments, which is the difference in the time scales at which relevant phenomena occur. Thermal systems are reacting orders of magnitude more slowly than electrical systems. The upper graph shows how relevant dynamic processes, excited by the heat generated during the experiment, continue for about 12 h afterwards. This is partially due to the unavailability of a large circulation pump at the time of the experiment; a much smaller pump had to be substituted and caused a low mass flow rate in the system. However, even with a much higher mass flow rate, the dynamic processes in the thermal system would still be orders of magnitude slower than in the electrical system.

The upper graph shows temperature measurements at different geographical locations along the heat network (see Figure 42 for reference). The first location ('Source') is the output of the heat source into the source's accumulator tank. It can be seen that the temperature profile closely tracks the electrical load. At the output of the accumulator tank (which corresponds to the input of the district heating system, labeled 'Line A in') the rapidly changing heat input has been smoothed to a single "heat impulse" which can then be observed to travel through network, past the different intermediate temperature sensors ('Line A.1' - 'Line A.2' - 'Line A.3' - 'Line B.3' - 'Line B.2' - 'Line B.1') towards the end of the network ('Line B.out') where a heat consumer is located. It can be seen that the amplitude of the impulse reduces over time (and distance). This is partially due to heat losses - insulation losses and energy expended to change the temperature of the pipe walls. Another factor can be observed as a "smearing effect" - the flanks of the impulse become less steep due to mixing effects and the heat

Figure 48: Dynamic response of the thermal network. Bottom graph: Electrical power consumption of the heat source, tracking the CHP's heat output. Top graph: Heat propagation through the network, measured at various points along the forward pipe.

conductivity of the pipe walls.

The graphs in Figure 48 only show the dynamic response of the forward lines of the network. A similar dynamic plays out on the return side. A glimpse of this can be seen towards the end of the recording, when the temperature at the start of the network drops to a value significantly lower than at the start of the experiment. This is due to cold return water from the heat consumer reaching the entrance of the network ('Line A in'). At this point in time, the heat source has been turned off for several hours, and the accumulator tank does not have enough energy left in it to counteract the continuous supply of cold water.

In summary, this section demonstrates the feasibility and effectiveness of performing Hardware-In-the-Loop and Geographically Distributed System to assess the robustness and responsiveness of multi-energy systems. Through the deployment of the JaNDER middleware and uAPI, secure and efficient communication was maintained across distributed RIs, facilitating real-time data exchange and operational control. The experimental demonstration provided insights into the potential to improve grid stability and provide flexibility by integrating power-to-heat services, addressing the critical needs of modern energy systems.

2.5 AC & ICT Co-Simulation

This demonstration concerns multi-domain systems combining an electrical grid and a networked ICT system; specifically such systems where the ICT system is used to control aspects of the electrical grid, such that the performance of the ICT system affects the performance of the electrical system. The primary contribution is the establishment of a test bed in which the flow of packets and messages can be traced and timestamped accurately, for the purpose of validating co-simulation tools combining the electrical and ICT domains.

2.5.1 Test description

Smart grids and energy systems are characterised by intricate interactions between the ICT domain and one or more energy domains. Currently, there are no established tool chains and validation approaches for comprehensively validating such systems.

This demonstration aims to present a proof-of-concept for such a validation approach. Its ultimate purpose is to analyse the capabilities of the co-simulation framework designed for simulating interactions between electrical grids and ICT networks which was developed in task JRA 2.1.1 (for detailed information, refer to Deliverable D11.1).

The original test case called for comparing the dynamics of the simulated system with those of two laboratory experiments:

- An experiment where an electrical grid and an ICT network are emulated in real-time, to be conducted at the SINTEF facility
- An experiment where a physical electrical grid is combined with an emulated ICT network in real-time, to be conducted at the DTU facility.

Due to the many obstacles encountered on the way, only the first of these two experiments could be completed by the time of release of this deliverable. Likewise, the comparison of the experimental results with the output of the co-simulation framework could not be completed. Both are expected to be demonstrated and the results published separately at a later date.

This demonstration serves as an initial step towards dedicated validation testing, aiming to explore the achievable performance range. The focus of this test is on quantifying the observed differences between simulation and reality, as well as identifying the factors influencing the attainable accuracy. The data collected during the experiments should enable the calibration of a reference scale (pass/fail).

The demonstration investigates a section of an electrical distribution grid containing flexibility assets, each of which belongs to one of two aggregators. These assets are dispatched by the aggregators in response to flexibility service requests from the distribution grid operator. A heterogeneous communication network facilitates data transfer between the distribution system operator, measurement equipment in the grid, flexibility assets, and aggregators.

The simulated system can be stimulated in two ways: through events within the communication network (e.g., equipment failure or limit violations) or within the electrical network. The testing explores the system's response to both types of events since they are expected to produce different dynamics due to varying degrees of coupling between the two simulated domains. Figure 49 provides an overview of the demonstration.

This demonstration aims to validate tools developed in WP11-JRA2, specifically the “*AC and ICT co-simulation framework*”. None of the services developed in WP12-JRA3 are included in this demonstration.

2.5.2 System abstraction and experiment design

In preparation of the experiments, a concrete test systems was developed based on the abstract test schematic in Figure 49.

Power System: The considered power system is a low voltage power distribution network with a radial topology. A physical laboratory configuration from SYSLAB (DTU), needed for the

Figure 49: A schematic representation of the “AC & ICT Co-Simulation” demonstration.

second experiment, was defined first and then used as a basis for deriving the emulated grid configuration at at SINTEF. It consists of a 2 km long feeder with nine buses and a total of nine loads which are connected to seven of the buses. Including four auxiliary buses used for load connection, the system has 13 buses overall. A simple schematic diagram of the power system topology is shown in Figure 50.

Figure 50: Power distribution grid used for the “AC & ICT Co-Simulation” emulation experiments.

The load characteristics used for the experiments are listed in Table 12. Three types of loads are being used:

- **Variable loads:** These loads are following a ramping function, linearly and continually increasing their power demand from the beginning to the end of the experiment. This increases the overall load on the feeder, forcing the DSO and aggregator to continuously adjust the amount of flexible demand committed to counteract the resulting voltage de-

cline.

- **Controllable loads:** These loads are considered flexible demand and can accept a request for load reduction by a variable amount relative to their calculated baseline consumption. It is assumed that the baseline consumption is known and therefore, the resulting instantaneous demand is always the result of a trivial subtraction. In the experiment configuration, this baseline is either a fixed value or a ramping function ('Variable and controllable').
- **Fixed loads:** These loads are set to a constant demand for the entire duration of the experiment.

Load	Size (in kW)	Type of Load
Load 1	20	Fixed
Load 2	12	Fixed
Load 3	25	Variable (not controllable)
Load 4	32	Controllable
Load 5	35	Fixed
Load 6	20	Variable (not controllable)
Load 7	20	Fixed
Load 8	25	Controllable
Load 9	10	Variable and controllable

Table 12: Loads used used in the "AC & ICT Co-Simulation" emulation experiment at SINTEF.

Control system: The control system consists of measurement equipment, a DSO dispatcher, two aggregators and three device controllers, one for each controllable load (loads 4, 8 and 9). Together, these entities form a closed-loop voltage regulator with the purpose of limiting voltage extremes across the distribution feeder. In the chosen configuration, one voltage meter at the end of the feeder continuously sends measurements to the DSO dispatcher which determines the appropriate amount of total demand reduction. The DSO dispatcher continuously polls the aggregators for the currently available demand flexibility. Based on each aggregator's available flexibility, the total demand reduction is split between aggregators, and the results of the split are sent to the aggregators in the form of demand reduction requests. One or more device controllers are assigned to each aggregator. The same process as between DSO dispatcher and aggregators plays out between aggregators and device controllers: The aggregator continuously polls the device controllers for available flexibility, then attempts to distribute the demand reduction request received from the DSO between the device controllers according to their available capacity. Finally, each device controller communicates the reduction request to its associated load, thereby closing the control loop.

Scenario Configuration: The experiment consists of two main scenarios triggering events from the power system and from within the communication system.

- In the first scenario, the three variable loads (loads 3, 6 and 9) are continuously increased to double their initial value with a ramp rate of 5 W s^{-1} . This serves as a base case to establish the undisturbed response of the voltage regulation mechanism.

In the second scenario, where the triggering events are from the communication system, a communication link failure is introduced between the DSO dispatch centre and aggregator 2 approximately three minutes after the start of the experiment.

Figure 51: Control system abstraction used in the experiments

2.5.3 Test execution

The first experiment – with emulations of both the electrical grid and the communication system – was conducted at the Norwegian National Smart Grid Laboratory in Trondheim, Norway, at the SINTEF facility. The test system consists of an emulation of the distribution power grid and a communication network for exchanging measurements and setpoints between the DSO, aggregators, and device controllers.

The power system is emulated using an OPAL RT real-time simulator. The loads at buses [4, 8, 9] are assumed to be flexible loads. These load points are equipped with device controllers that can receive setpoints from aggregators using the OPC-UA protocol. It is assumed that the aggregators can reduce up to 50 % of these controllable loads. Voltage measurements are collected from the bus at the end of the radial grid (bus 13) and are sent to the DSO dispatch centre via OPC-UA protocol.

Communication System: For communication between the field devices (power system), DSO, and aggregators, the OPC-UA protocol is used. An OPC server is configured on the OPAL-RT emulator, while OPC clients are used at the DSO and aggregators. The client at the DSO is used to read voltage measurements, and the clients at the device controllers are used to send setpoints to the OPC-UA server on the OPAL-RT emulator. A custom REST web services implementation is used for the communication between the DSO and aggregators in order to exchange flexibility information and demand reduction requests. In order to simplify an already complex setup, it was decided not to make the connection between aggregators and device controllers an explicit communication link in the first experiment: Aggregators and device controllers exchange data through plain function calls between objects, allowing the experiment to

Figure 52: Communication network setup used in the “AC & ICT Co-Simulation” emulation experiment at SINTEF.

focus on the network link between DSO and aggregators.

Data Collection: Data is collected at the application layer from the DSO and aggregators, exported in Comma Separated Values (CSV) format with detailed information such as the type of control signals, along with their respective timestamps. Additionally, `tcpdump` is used to collect network data at each - physical and virtual - network interface of the Linux machines hosting the DSO and aggregator applications. The power system data, including voltage measurements, setpoints for the flexible loads, and power measurements at all load points, are collected in `.mat` format on the OPAL RT emulator.

2.5.4 Network emulation, methods and challenges

The communication network connecting the DSO, aggregators, and individual device controllers at the flexible loads is modelled as a wide area network using the emulation tool `Mininet`⁶. Various methods were employed to model the network components including the DSO, aggregators, and device controllers. The initial approach involved modelling all the different elements on a single Linux machine where the Mininet network emulation was also running. However, routing between the DSO and aggregators through the Mininet network, with all components running on the same host machine, proved complex as the operating system’s local routing interfered with the Mininet routing. Running the DSO and aggregator algorithms on Mininet’s virtual hosts was considered, but issues in clock synchronisation among these virtual hosts emerged, making time synchronisation challenging to correct. Network namespaces were also considered, but they faced similar time synchronisation issues after preliminary data analysis.

Method Applied: The final setup of the communication system, as shown in Figure 52, consists of three Linux machines: one modelling the DSO dispatch centre, another modelling two aggregators, and the third running the Mininet wide area network emulation. All these devices

⁶<https://mininet.org/>

including the OPAL-RT emulator were connected to a hardware clock, SEL2488, for precise time synchronisation, as the use case requires millisecond-level comparison of physical and emulation experiments with the co-simulation tool. Network Time Protocol (NTP) was used to synchronise each of these Linux machines to the hardware clock.

Linux machine 3 is central, modelling the wide area network using Mininet. OVS switches in Mininet serve as interfaces where physical Ethernet ports connected to the DSO and aggregator devices are bridged to the OVS switches in Mininet. A Gaussian distribution delay was applied to the links connecting the OVS switch, modelling the wide area network characteristics. A NAT service on this machine enables all devices to communicate with the OPAL RT power system emulator and the SEL2488 hardware clock, both located outside the emulated wide area network (in the laboratory LAN network).

2.5.5 Results

Figure 53 summaries the control impact on the distribution feeder simulated in OPAL RT. The topmost graph shows the total load on the feeder (i.e. the combined demand of the six uncontrollable and three controllable loads) as measured at the point of grid connection. The load curve is a superposition of three developments:

- Several of the loads are programmed to follow a constant upwards ramp in order to excite the voltage regulation algorithm. On its own, this would create a monotonously increasing feeder load.
- The controllable loads respond to two events, leading to step reductions in load: At $t = 20\text{ s}$, the voltage regulation algorithm is enabled. As the feeder voltage is already below the nominal voltage at this point, the voltage regulator immediately responds with a load reduction request to both aggregators. It can be seen that the two aggregators and their loads respond at slightly different times, leading to a two-step response. At $t = 123\text{ s}$, aggregator 2 has lost connection to the voltage regulation algorithm; as a result, load 3 does not receive further load reduction requests. Upon detection of the communication failure, the voltage regulation algorithm assumes that the reduction setpoint for load 3 has reset to zero, as a worst case scenario. The entire reduction demand for aggregator 2 is therefore redistributed to aggregator 1. This results in another step reduction as load 1 and load 2 are picking up the reduction demand previously allocated to load 3.
- As the overall load increases due to the programmed ramps and the voltage at the end of the feeder drops correspondingly, the voltage regulation algorithm slowly increases the amount of load reduction requested from the aggregators. As a result, the load increase deviates from a linear curve as the gradient of the load ramp is gradually flattening out.

The second graph from the top shows the effective power consumption of controllable loads 1, 2 and 3, i.e. the base consumption of each load minus the requested load reduction. The requested load reduction for each load is shown in the third graph from the top.

It can be seen that loads 1 and 2 have a constant consumption before the reduction, while load 3 is following a ramp. After the loss of aggregator 2, load 3 does not participate in the voltage regulation anymore and follows a constant ramp, whereas a greater reduction is requested from loads 1 and 2 to compensate for the loss of load 3.

The bottom graph shows the voltage at the end of the feeder, i.e. furthest from the grid connection point. Both of the events mentioned above can be seen here as well: The initial DSO

response results in a voltage relief, whereas the loss of aggregator 2 causes a temporary voltage sag until the voltage controller has adapted to the new situation.

Figure 53: Electrical system response. Top graph: Total feeder loading at PCC. Second from top: Effective power consumption (constant demand minus requested reduction) of controllable loads 1-3. Third from top: Load reduction for controllable loads 1-3 as requested by aggregators. Bottom graph: Voltage at end of feeder.

3 KPIs for Enhanced Capabilities for Extended RIs

Within the scope of the task JRA4.1, a range of KPIs have been formulated. These KPIs, detailed in the Deliverable D13.1, serve as the means to assess the effectiveness of the extended ERIGrid 2.0 RIs and provide valuable insights into their suitability for addressing important research inquiries within the community.

The KPIs for the five distinct demonstration cases in WP13-JRA4 (see Section 2 for an overview of the accomplished demos) are structured around a set of questions and questionnaires. Specifically, these questions are divided into two categories. The first group focuses on general inquiries primarily concerning management aspects, making them of potential interest to non-technical stakeholders, industrial clients, or academics with specific interests. The second category delves into the technical questions that are tailored to each individual demonstration. Researchers affiliated with the participating RIs have completed these questions at various stages, including preparation, execution, and evaluation of the experiments featured in the demonstrations.

This document provides an analysis of the outcomes. To maintain clarity and conciseness, the subsequent section discusses the key findings from the questionnaires, while the questions and their respective answers are available in Appendix B.

3.1 General Questions

This section aims to summarise the answers to general questions related to the various demonstrations conducted within the ERIGrid 2.0 project. These KPIs, detailed in Deliverable D13.1, play a pivotal role in assessing the effectiveness of the extended ERIGrid 2.0 RIs and offer valuable insights into their suitability for addressing significant research inquiries within the community. The outcomes of the various demonstrations highlight both commonalities and differences in their contributions and importance to the strategic targets and professional development of the participating RIs.

In the “Improved Stability and Accuracy for PHIL” demonstration (Section 3.2), the primary issue addressed was the stability and accuracy limitations of existing PHIL interface algorithms. This demonstration added value by enhancing the accuracy, scalability, scientific expertise, and services extensions for the involved RIs. The importance of this demonstration was deemed large for the strategic targets and moderate for the professional development of the lab staff, with the experimental setup requiring seven days each for preparation and conduction. The improvements were rated as “moderate” (level 3 over 5) on the scale of changes and improvements. The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) was at level 9, indicating a high degree of maturity. The importance to strategic targets was rated as “large” (level 4 over 5), and the cost-saving was also considered “moderate” (level 3 over 5).

The “Time Delay Compensation for GDRTS” demonstration (Section 3.3) tackled the detrimental accuracy issues in GDRTS due to time delay variability. This demonstration introduced a novel DDPG + LSTM algorithm-based DRL agent to enhance delay compensation, significantly improving the accuracy, temporal resolution, and scalability of GDRTS setups. This demonstration also had a large strategic importance for the participating RIs and a moderate impact on professional development, with a considerable preparation time of 365 days and a conduction time of 14 days. The improvements were “moderate” (level 3 over 5), with the TRL at level 6. The importance to strategic targets was “large” (level 4 over 5), and the cost-saving was “moderate” (level 3 over 5).

The “Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for Remote RI Testing” (Section 3.4) demonstration focused on simplifying the configuration process of GD-RTS experiments involving multiple RIs. By automating the configuration process and using tools like VILLASnode, JaNDER, uAPI, and CM, this demonstration improved the scalability and service extensions for the involved RIs. The strategic importance and professional development impacts were both rated as large, with a substantial preparation time of 168 days and a conduction time of 12 days. The improvements were rated as “moderate” (level 3 over 5), the TRL at level 5, and the importance to strategic targets and lab staff professional development was “large” (level 4 over 5). The cost-saving was also considered “moderate” (level 3 over 5).

The “Multi-Energy District Flexibility” (Section 3.5) demonstration examined the provision of power-to-heat services within a local multi-energy district, assessing their impact on both electric and thermal networks. This demonstration improved the accuracy, temporal resolution, scalability, and service extensions by using real hardware interconnected and synchronised with software tools developed in previous WPs. It had a large impact on the infrastructure improvements and a moderate strategic importance for the participating RIs, requiring about 10 days for conduction and up to a couple of months for preparation. The improvements were “large” (level 4 over 5), with a TRL of 6. The importance to strategic targets was “moderate” (level 3 over 5), and the cost-saving was “moderate” (level 3 over 5).

Lastly, the “AC & ICT Co-Simulation” (Section 3.6) demonstration addressed the integration of power system and ICT components in smart grids, using the Mosaik framework for co-simulation. This demonstration enhanced the accuracy, temporal resolution, scalability, and service extensions for the involved RIs by validating the co-simulation approach against physical experiments. The strategic importance and professional development impacts were rated as moderate, with a preparation period of up to a couple of months and a conduction time of approximately 15 days. The improvements were “moderate” (level 3 over 5), with a TRL of 5-6. The importance to strategic targets and professional development was “moderate” (level 3 over 5). The cost-saving was “large” (level 4 over 5).

In summary, while each demonstration addressed unique problems and offered specific advancements, common points include their significant contributions to the strategic targets and professional development of the participating RIs, as well as improvements in accuracy, scalability, and service extensions. The preparation and conduction times varied, reflecting the complexity and scope of each demonstration. These demonstrations collectively underscore the enhanced capabilities and strategic value provided by the advanced methods and services developed within the ERIGrid 2.0 project.

3.2 Improved Stability and Accuracy for PHIL

This section presents the outcomes of assessments conducted via questionnaires by researchers from the participating RIs during the preparation, execution, and evaluation of experiments within the “Improved Stability and Accuracy for PHIL” demonstration. This demonstration specifically addresses the problem of extending the range of stable PHIL simulation setups, motivated by the limitations in stability and accuracy of existing PHIL interface algorithms. Despite various interface algorithms being developed over the years, most still suffer from instabilities at high impedance ratios or compromised accuracy. These assessments provide a comprehensive understanding of various aspects related to flexibility, operational limits, and performance within the participating RIs. Key findings from these assessments are discussed here, while detailed questions and corresponding answers can be found in Appendix B.

The responses indicate that the stability region for PHIL experiments with Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation (VSIDC) improved by 500 % compared to the LPF-based V-ITM method, ensuring stability for impedance ratios up to 5. Accuracy improvements include a 0.39 % error for active power and 2.56 % for reactive power. The maximum errors in steady-state active and reactive power exchange at the PCC with VSIDC are 1.64 % and 11.35 % for feedback filter metrics and 1.25 % and 8.79 % for VSI metrics, respectively. Although transient event accuracy was not thoroughly evaluated, VSI presents better accuracy at the stability limit.

In summary, the results of the assessments indicate significant progress in research capabilities, operational efficiency, and system integration within the ERIGrid 2.0 project. Despite some challenges, the findings highlight advancements toward the project's strategic goals, paving the way for future research and development in the area of improved stability and accuracy for PHIL.

3.3 Time Delay Compensation for GDRTS

This section depicts the outcomes of assessments conducted via questionnaires by researchers from the participating RIs during the idea formulation, theoretical analysis, execution, and experimental evaluation of GDRTS time delay characterisation and compensation experiments within the “Time Delay Compensation for GDRTS” demonstration. This demonstration aimed to address the limitations of conventional time delay compensation methods, particularly regarding adaptability to variable time delays. These assessments provide a comprehensive overview of the feasibility, applicability, limitations, and advantages of both the conventional time delay compensation method and the proposed DDPG+LSTM aided time delay compensation method within the participating RIs. Key findings from these assessments are discussed in this section, with detailed questions and corresponding answers available in Appendix B.

By supporting this demonstration and validating the proposed DDPG+LSTM aided adaptive time delay compensation scheme, the participating RIs made significant contributions to the characterisation of the time delay within the GDRTS setup, as presented in Section 2.2.1, and the verification of the time delay compensation methods. The response and analysis of the demonstration results, depicted in Section 2.2.4 from all participating RIs, indicate a remarkable improvement in GDRTS simulations setups with enhanced power synchronisation capability and improved simulation accuracy. Above all, the demonstration of the two cases for scenario 4 in Section 2.2.4 effectively verify the enhanced adaptability of the DDPG+LSTM aided adaptive time delay compensation scheme to variable delays in GDRTS setup. These advancements are crucial in facilitating the widespread adoption of GDRTS simulations techniques among all RIs.

Overall, the outcomes of the assessments indicate some moderate advancements in research capabilities, operational efficiency, and system integration of geographically distributed RIs within the ERIGrid 2.0 project. Even though a variety of challenges encountered in the demonstration process, the results demonstrate progress toward achieving the ultimate objectives of the project, with significant implications for promoting the research and development and the widespread adoption GDRTS techniques.

3.4 Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for Remote RI Testing

This section presents the outcomes of assessments conducted via questionnaires by researchers from the participating RIs during the preparation, execution, and evaluation of experiments within the “Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for Remote RI Testing” demonstration. The main goal of this demonstration was to implement tools for improving the process of setting up multi-RI scenarios involving CHIL and PHIL. We identified that one of the most important aspects affecting the time for this process is the configuration of simulators, devices and software modules including the lab coupling tools, which is not only a tedious process, but also a process in which the human errors can represent additional delays and, in the worst case, the affection of devices, representing high costs for reparation and replacement. Moreover, the time-to-experiment benefits from code reuse, which requires a harmonisation layer in the experiment’s communications. Additionally, this time can be reduced by decreasing the times spent on related administrative processes, mainly those related to the implementation of firewall rules to allow communications between laboratories.

To fulfil the main goal of Demo3, the lab coupling tool VILLASnode and the CM tool were improved. Particularly, VILLASnode was improved to incorporate the WebRTC technology, which allows to use standard communication protocols and ports, thus eliminating the administrative burden related to the implementation of firewall rules. Moreover, we also used JaNDER, which made this demonstration the first multi-RI experiment using multiple lab coupling tools. In this case, the uAPI was used in conjunction with JaNDER. This allowed the reuse of code and related time savings, since the RI adapter in RWTH was implemented mostly based on an existing solution provided by SINTEF. The CM tool can potentially reduce the configuration time by at least 50 % in the case of an experiment involving two RIs, since both the initial configuration and any configuration change have to be implemented only once, and the configuration files for all the involved RIs is automatically generated by the CM tool.

3.5 Multi-Energy District Flexibility

This section presents the outcomes of the assessments conducted via questionnaires by researchers from the participating RIs during the preparation, execution, or evaluation of experiments within the “Multi-Energy District Flexibility” demonstration. These assessments provide a comprehensive understanding of various aspects related to flexibility, operational limits, and performance within the participating RIs. Here, we discuss the key findings derived from these assessments, while the detailed questions and corresponding answers can be found in Appendix B.

The responses indicate a moderate improvement in flexibility observed among the participating RIs, which holds significant strategic importance. This enhancement directly contributes to advancing research capabilities in multi-energy systems, aligning closely with the overarching mission of the RIs to drive innovation in energy-related research and development. By enhancing the coordination and optimisation of thermal and electrical energy usage, this level of improvement represents a pivotal step toward achieving broader strategic targets set forth by the RIs.

Furthermore, no violations were reported regarding electrical energy or power limits within the participating RIs, indicating a high level of adherence to operational thresholds. This underscores the validity and effectiveness of the services developed within WP11-JRA2 and WP12-JRA3, demonstrating the extended RI’s ability to offer new services. Additionally, this ensures that systems operate within designated parameters without exceeding defined limits.

Similarly, no deviations were observed in electrical energy or power exchange setpoints at the PCC during the evaluation period. Any variations that occurred were negligible, highlighting the consistency and stability of the exchange setpoints throughout the assessment. Whereas, regarding deviations in thermal setpoints within the participating RIs, they were found to be negligible, indicating minimal variations that did not significantly impact system performance. This underscores the stability and effectiveness of the thermal management systems implemented within the RIs.

Despite challenges in quantifying the reduction of thermal and electrical power losses, primarily due to hardware issues and logistical constraints, the “Multi-Energy District Flexibility” demonstration in WP13-JRA4 yielded positive results. Although the focus was not on showcasing the magnitude of power loss reduction, the demonstrations received excellent feedback, indicating their effectiveness in real-world scenarios. Indeed, significant increases in both electrical and thermal capacities were observed in the experiment compared to a single RI setup. These enhancements demonstrate the improved capacity and capabilities achieved through system integration and collaboration among RIs.

In summary, the outcomes of the assessments reflect positive advancements in research capabilities, operational efficiency, and system integration within the ERIGrid 2.0 project. Despite challenges encountered, the results demonstrate progress toward achieving the strategic objectives of the project, with implications for future research and development efforts in the field of multi-energy systems.

3.6 AC & ICT Co-Simulation

This section discusses the assessments conducted via questionnaires by researchers from the participating RIs during the preparation and execution of experiments within the “AC & ICT Co-Simulation” demonstration. These assessments are preliminary at this stage; due to a higher than expected complexity of the test setup and the need to revise the implementation several times, only the first of two planned experiments could be conducted in time for the deliverable, and the key evaluation step for calculating the premeditated metrics - comparison with the results of a co-simulation setup matching that of the physical tests - could not be performed yet. Hence, no meaningful accuracy metrics could be calculated at this point.

It is planned to complete and publish the work within the ERIGrid 2.0 project; these planned future publications are expected to yield the quantitative results required for KPI evaluation.

With the clarity of hindsight, the project team believes that at least some of the KPIs of demonstration 5 should have chosen to relate to the development of capabilities, knowledge, joint tools and infrastructure, instead of exclusively focusing on technical measurements obtainable only at the end of a fully complete and successful test campaign.

The primary results of the activities of demonstration 5 at the time of writing of this deliverable are the network emulation method developed for the first experiment, as described in Section 2.5.4, and an automated processing tool for tracking messages and events across the network. Both are indispensable components for executing the tests. Both are also reusable tools which will be able to be used for a wider range of experiments investigating the interaction between physical energy system components and data networking.

The full extent of the need for developing these tools did not become apparent until after the first attempts to execute the tests. In particular, the magnitude of the detrimental impact on timestamp accuracy of using containerization for the deployment of distributed network emula-

tion components, was not foreseen at the beginning of the test campaign. Having these tools and methods available (and having identified the shortcomings of alternative approaches) will allow other researchers to save time and provides a faster route to better data.

In this context, even the current intermediate results of demonstration 5 contribute to the strategic objectives of the ERIGrid 2.0 project: Developing and demonstrating new research capabilities, methods and tools for efficient testing and system integration.

The detailed questions and corresponding answers can be found in Appendix B.

4 Conclusions

The ERIGrid 2.0 project, through its advanced methods and services developed in WP11-JRA2 and WP12-JRA3, has significantly enhanced the capabilities of RIs. This enhancement has been effectively demonstrated and assessed in WP13-JRA4. The integration of simulators, HIL systems, and physical labs into a single extended infrastructure has greatly expanded the testing capabilities of individual facilities. This integration not only increases the number of feasible test cases but also allows access to additional domains provided by other facilities, either through simulation or physical components.

Starting from the holistic test descriptions in JRA4.1, detailed in Deliverable D13.1, several test cases have been conducted through the integration of RIs as developed in JRA4.2, with results presented in Deliverable D13.2. The fully established extended RI has facilitated experimental activities within task JRA4.3, whose outcomes have been collected and described in this deliverable, D13.3. These experiments demonstrate various extended services, including simulation, HIL, laboratory facilities, and their combinations. The experiments range from single-environment RIs to multiple-environment RIs, combining simulation, HIL, and hardware elements.

The key objectives of this document were to:

- Demonstrate the ability of the extended RI to provide new services.
- Evaluate the results of tests conducted to showcase the capabilities of the extended RI and its advantages.
- Assess the KPIs, as defined in Deliverable D13.1, to evaluate the capabilities achieved through the advanced methods and services developed.

This document provided an overview of the demonstrations developed in Deliverable D13.1, detailing their requirements and the results that illustrate the extended RI's ability to offer new services. It also presented and analysed the outcomes from the KPI questionnaires designed to evaluate the extended capabilities of the RIs. These include generic questionnaires applicable to all demonstrations and specific ones tailored to individual demonstrations.

In summary, the experiments conducted and the results obtained underscored the effectiveness of the extended RI in providing enhanced services and capabilities. The integration of multiple RIs has not only broadened the scope of possible test cases but has also validated the advanced methods and services developed within the ERIGrid 2.0 project. This comprehensive assessment highlights the significant strides made in enhancing RI capabilities, offering valuable insights for future research and development efforts in multi-energy systems.

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Appendix A: Extended Services

WP12-JRA3 involves the development of a comprehensive set of services designed to enhance the interconnection of geographically separated RIs. To enhance the reader's experience while going through this Deliverable, the Appendix conveniently lists all the WP12-JRA3 services described within it. This eliminates the need for readers to refer back to a previous deliverable. Therefore, the Appendix offers concise descriptions of all the services developed in WP12-JRA3.

A.1 Virtual Overlay Network

Geographically Distributed Simulation (GDSim) or experiment requires the establishment of a communication link between the two (or more) RIs involved. Direct communication between different RIs can be restricted due to security concerns. To address this concern, a transparent overlay network is established between the RIs to be interconnected. This overlay network employs Virtual Private Network (VPN) solutions to create a mesh of peer-to-peer connections between all RIs. The implementation of the virtual overlay network has been tested within the scope of WP11-JRA2, establishing a peer-peer connection between up to three RIs.

A.2 Provisioning and Orchestration

To facilitate the equipment within a RI to communicate with equipment within other RIs, a gateway that implements the virtual overlay network is required. This is enabled through a mobile unit – a mobile computing device acting as a gateway between a RI equipment and other remote RI. Provisioning refers to the automatic setup and maintenance of these units, removing the human from the loop, saving time and effort. In a similar manner, orchestration refers to the management of GDS setups and sequence of experiments through scripts.

A.3 Data Exchange

Each RI with the combination of equipment, data formats, communications protocols and practices is unique. A GDS would typically involve the exchange of data between the interconnected RIs. To facilitate the seamless exchange of data, a service that enables interfacing multiple data formats and protocols is integrated. This service further allows the capability to control the rate of data transmission between the RIs.

A.4 Network Monitoring

The geographical distances between the RIs to be interconnected introduce large latencies that can impact the accuracy and stability of the GDS. To understand the impact of the latencies and to adopt mitigating measures to alleviate their deteriorating impact, a measurement of these latencies is required. In addition, understanding the detailed status of the communication network (such as the bandwidth, packet loss, throughput, etc.) can allow for the development of advanced techniques to mitigate the impact of the latencies. For this purpose, a network monitoring service is under development that utilises the well-established perfSonar⁷ tool suite

⁷<https://www.perfsonar.net/>

adapted for the use in Kubernetes clusters.

A.5 Network Emulation

Many smart grid controls are relying upon communications, particularly distributed and centralised control schemes. Incorporation of realistic communication characteristics in experimental evaluations is desirable rather than the use of static delays. This service offers the RIs to incorporate realistic emulation of real-world network characteristics when undertaking single RI or GDS. It further allows the users to configure one or more traffic profiles to impair network traffic between the interconnected RIs.

A.6 Time-Synchronization

This service is developed to allow for a common time base for appropriate temporal alignment of experimental results obtained through the interconnection of multiple RIs. Time synchronisation is provided through Global Positioning System (GPS), NTP, or the Precision Time Protocol (PTP).

Appendix B: Key Performance Index Q&A

This appendix contains an in-depth examination of the KPIs formulated within the framework of task JRA4.1. These KPIs, detailed in Deliverable D13.1, play a pivotal role in assessing the effectiveness of the extended ERIGrid 2.0 RIs and offer valuable insights into their suitability for addressing significant research inquiries within the community. Here, compilation of questions and their corresponding answers for each demonstration is reported, offering a detailed examination of the assessment process.

B.1 General Questions

B.1.1 Improved Stability and Accuracy for PHIL

1. WHICH PROBLEM IS ADDRESSED IN DEMONSTRATION NO. 1?

Extended range of stable PHIL simulation setups.

2. WHAT IS THE MOTIVATION FOR SOLVING THIS PROBLEM?

Limitations with regards to stability/accuracy of existing PHIL interface algorithms.

3. WHAT IS THE EXISTING STATE OF THE ART FOR SOLVING THIS PROBLEM?

Various interface algorithms have been developed in the previous years but still most of them suffer from instabilities at high impedance ratios or compromised accuracy.

4. WHAT ARE THE ADDED VALUES OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 1 COMPARED TO THE STATE-OF-THE-ART IN TERMS OF (A) ACCURACY, (B) TEMPORAL RESOLUTION, (C) SCALABILITY, (D) SCIENTIFIC EXPERTISE OF THE INVOLVED RIs, (E) SERVICES EXTENSIONS FOR THE INVOLVED RI/PARTNERS

The “Improved Stability and Accuracy for PHIL” demonstration adds values compared to the state-of-the-art by improving the accuracy, scalability, scientific expertise, and services extensions for the involved RIs and partners.

5. PLEASE QUANTIFY THE TIME FOR CONDUCTION OF THE EXPERIMENTS OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 1! (DAYS OF LAB USAGE)

7 days were required (this concerns only the final experimentation).

6. PLEASE QUANTIFY THE TIME FOR PREPARATION OF THE EXPERIMENTS OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 1! (TIME TO EXPERIMENT IN DAYS)

7 days were required.

7. HOW LARGE ARE THE CHANGES/IMPROVEMENTS OF THE PARTICIPATING RIs COMPARED TO THE SITUATION BEFORE? USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

The change and improvements to the participating RI infrastructures brought about the demonstration can be characterised as “moderate”, corresponding to the level 3 on the scale.

8. QUANTIFY THE COST-SAVINGS OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 1 COMPARED TO OTHER SOLUTIONS USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

The cost-saving of the demonstration compared to the other simulations can be quantified as “moderate”, corresponding to level 3 on the scale. Specifically, there was no need for acquisition of hardware impedances for PHIL experimentation.

9. WHAT IS THE STATUS (I.E., TRL) OF THE EXPERIMENT IMPLEMENTATION COMPARED TO THE STATE OF THE ART?

The status (TRL) of the experiment implementation in this demonstration compared with the existing PHIL interface algorithms is at a TRL-9

10. HOW IMPORTANT IS DEMONSTRATION NO. 1 TO THE STRATEGIC TARGETS OF THE PARTICIPATING RIs? (GIVE EXAMPLES) USE THE SCALE WITH THE FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

The demonstration is of “large” importance to the strategic targets of the participating RIs. It is expected to support the long-term PHIL testing objectives of ICCS concerning applications of grid-forming inverters, multi-energy systems, and cybersecurity V-ITM. One of the participating laboratories is expanding its work and capabilities regarding the testing of grid forming inverters, based on this development.

11. HOW IMPORTANT IS DEMONSTRATION NO. 1 TO THE LAB STAFF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE PARTICIPATING RIs? (GIVE EXAMPLES) USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

The demonstration is of “moderate” importance to the professional development of the lab staff at the participating RIs. A high quality journal publication has occurred, and the participating lab staff has presented the current solutions to conference panel sessions and invited talks.

B.1.2 Time Delay Compensation for GDRTS

1. WHICH PROBLEM IS ADDRESSED IN DEMONSTRATION NO. 2?

The detrimental accuracy issues of GDRTS arising from time delay variability in conventional compensation methods have been addressed in this demonstration using a proposed DDPG+LSTM algorithm-based DRL agent to aid delay compensation.

2. WHAT IS THE MOTIVATION FOR SOLVING THIS PROBLEM?

The primary motivation for this demonstration is to enhance the accuracy of real-world GDRTS experimental simulations. This improvement addresses significant accuracy issues caused by the variable time delays in the GDRTS system, thereby promoting its widespread adoption and facilitating large-scale power system simulations using this method.

3. WHAT IS THE EXISTING STATE OF THE ART FOR SOLVING THIS PROBLEM?

The existing state-of-the-art methods for addressing GDRTS accuracy issues stemming from time delays rely on the utilisation of DFT or dq-frame additional phase delay addition methods. However, these approaches assume a fixed delay or use only the average time delay value in the GDRTS system, neglecting the impact of delay variability on delay compensation performance and power signal synchronisation.

4. WHAT ARE THE ADDED VALUES OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 2 COMPARED TO THE STATE-OF-THE-ART IN TERMS OF (A) ACCURACY, (B) TEMPORAL RESOLUTION, (C) SCALABILITY,

(D) SCIENTIFIC EXPERTISE OF THE INVOLVED RIs, (E) SERVICES EXTENSIONS FOR THE INVOLVED RI/PARTNERS

The “Time Delay Compensation for GDRTS” demonstration

- (a) **ACCURACY:** Building upon the existing state-of-the-art methods, the proposed DDPG + LSTM algorithm-based DRL agent in this demonstration significantly enhances the accuracy of the GDRTS setup. As shown in Table 8, compared to the current state-of-the-art methods, the proposed approach effectively compensates for variable time delays in the GDRTS setup. This results in significantly reduced power tracking errors and power signal synchronisation errors, achieving enhanced accuracy.
 - (b) **TEMPORAL RESOLUTION:** This demonstration fills the research gap by providing a comprehensive characterisation of time delay within the GDRTS setup and proposing a novel DRL-aided time delay compensation method. This approach enables adaptive compensation for time delay variability. These advancements offer in-depth insights into time delay characterisation within the GDRTS setup and result in a more robust GDRTS system with enhanced fidelity.
 - (c) **SCALABILITY:** Compared to the existing state-of-the-art methods, the proposed DDPG + LSTM algorithm-based adaptive delay compensation in this demonstration offers enhanced scalability. It enables a more accurate geographically distributed co-simulation environment, supporting large-scale power system simulations.
 - (d) **SCIENTIFIC EXPERTISE OF THE INVOLVED RIs:** By participating in this demonstration, researchers in the involved RIs played a crucial role in its success. The scientific expertise of these RIs in building and implementing a robust GDRTS system with improved accuracy has been significantly enhanced.
 - (e) **SERVICES EXTENSIONS FOR THE INVOLVED RI/PARTNERS:** Compared to existing state-of-the-art methods, the proposed DDPG+LSTM algorithm-based delay compensation method equips the GDRTS system with adaptivity to time delay variability and enhanced accuracy. This supports the widespread adoption of the GDRTS system and enhances the interconnection capability among all involved RIs.
5. PLEASE QUANTIFY THE TIME FOR CONDUCTION OF THE EXPERIMENTS OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 2! (DAYS OF LAB USAGE)
- The time required for conducting this demonstration primarily depends on the system design process, DRL agent training, deployment and experimental validation. The time for conducting this demonstration is 14 days. This time frame accounts for the time used for time delay data collection and characterisation, as well as the agent training and its experimental validation.
6. PLEASE QUANTIFY THE TIME FOR PREPARATION OF THE EXPERIMENTS OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 2! (TIME TO EXPERIMENT IN DAYS)
- The time to experiment required for conducting this demonstration is 365 days. This time frame accounts for the time used for time delay data collection and characterisation, as well as the agent training and its experimental validation.
7. HOW LARGE ARE THE CHANGES/IMPROVEMENTS OF THE PARTICIPATING RIs COMPARED TO THE SITUATION BEFORE? USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

The degree of changes/improvements of the participating RIs compared to the situation before can be characterised as “moderate”.

8. QUANTIFY THE COST-SAVINGS OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 2 COMPARED TO OTHER SOLUTIONS USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

The cost-savings of this demonstration can be quantified as “moderate”.

9. WHAT IS THE STATUS (I.E., TRL) OF THE EXPERIMENT IMPLEMENTATION COMPARED TO THE STATE OF THE ART?

Compared to the existing state-of-the-art, the TRL level of the experiment implementation in this demonstration is TRL-6, indicating significant advancements beyond the current state-of-the-art.

10. HOW IMPORTANT IS DEMONSTRATION NO. 2 TO THE STRATEGIC TARGETS OF THE PARTICIPATING RIs? (GIVE EXAMPLES) USE THE SCALE WITH THE FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

The importance of this demonstration No. 2 to the strategic targets of the participating RIs can be characterised as “large”, as this facilitates the interconnection of participating RIs with enhanced accuracy.

11. HOW IMPORTANT IS DEMONSTRATION NO. 2 TO THE LAB STAFF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE PARTICIPATING RIs? (GIVE EXAMPLES) USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

The importance of this demonstration No. 2 to the lab staff professional development of the participating RIs can be characterised as “moderate”, as this enhances their expertise in designing and implementing GDRTS system and its delay compensation.

B.1.3 Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for Remote RI Testing

1. WHICH PROBLEM IS ADDRESSED IN DEMONSTRATION NO. 3?

The problem is the complexity of setting up Geographically Distributed Real-Time Co-simulation (GD-RTS) experiments involving more than two RIs and making configuration changes to it. Normally, it takes a lot of effort for the manual configuration of these experiments. Additionally, given the high number of protocols and data formats, RIs need to spend a lot of effort developing software modules for protocol conversion.

2. WHAT IS THE MOTIVATION FOR SOLVING THIS PROBLEM?

The main motivation is to reduce the time and effort spent on the implementation of GD-RTS scenarios. With GD-RTS, extended RIs can be achieved, in which the involved RIs can share resources to achieve more realistic power system simulations.

3. WHAT IS THE EXISTING STATE OF THE ART FOR SOLVING THIS PROBLEM?

The existing state-of-the-art relates to the CM concept, which aims to provide a methodology by which the configuration process of hardware and software assets can be automated. The concept was heavily addressed in the 90s and early 2000s (Dart, 1991; Conradi & Westfechtel, 1998; Hass, 2003). Recently, CM methodologies are subject of improvements, given by the introduction of Continuous Deployment / Continuous Integration

(CI/CD) and the Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC) paradigm (Farayola, Hassan, Adaramodu, Fakeyede, & Oladeinde, 2023).

4. WHAT ARE THE ADDED VALUES OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 3 COMPARED TO THE STATE-OF-THE-ART IN TERMS OF (A) ACCURACY, (B) TEMPORAL RESOLUTION, (C) SCALABILITY, (D) SCIENTIFIC EXPERTISE OF THE INVOLVED RIs, (E) SERVICES EXTENSIONS FOR THE INVOLVED RI/PARTNERS

The “Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for Remote RI Testing” demonstration

(a) ACCURACY: None.

(b) TEMPORAL RESOLUTION: None.

(c) SCALABILITY: Improves scalability of multi-RI experiments by automating their configuration process.

(d) SCIENTIFIC EXPERTISE OF THE INVOLVED RIs: None.

(e) SERVICES EXTENSIONS FOR THE INVOLVED RI/PARTNERS: By means of the configuration management process and the use of the uAPI we expect to extend the capabilities of the RIs, since the setup of multi-RI experiments is simplified.

5. PLEASE QUANTIFY THE TIME FOR CONDUCTION OF THE EXPERIMENTS OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 3! (DAYS OF LAB USAGE)

12. This is only for executing the experiments, after they were prepared.

6. PLEASE QUANTIFY THE TIME FOR PREPARATION OF THE EXPERIMENTS OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 3! (TIME TO EXPERIMENT IN DAYS)

168 (5 months multiplied by 70 % of dedication plus 3 months multiplied by 70 % of dedication for the integration of the remaining RIs).

7. HOW LARGE ARE THE CHANGES/IMPROVEMENTS OF THE PARTICIPATING RIs COMPARED TO THE SITUATION BEFORE? USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

Moderate. On average, some infrastructures like RWTH and TEC improved substantially in their process of carrying out multi-RI experiments. While other RIs were well prepared for these experiments and not much improvement was required. Finally, other RIs gained knowledge on the use of tools like VILLASnode, but it was not enough to make relevant improvements to their RI.

8. QUANTIFY THE COST-SAVINGS OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 3 COMPARED TO OTHER SOLUTIONS USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

Moderate. The costs related to the time spent to configure a multi-RI experiment can be of at least 50 % less considering an experiment with two RIs.

9. WHAT IS THE STATUS (I.E., TRL) OF THE EXPERIMENT IMPLEMENTATION COMPARED TO THE STATE OF THE ART?

We would place this demonstration in the TRL level 5: Early demonstrations of the use of the technology were carried out.

10. HOW IMPORTANT IS DEMONSTRATION NO. 3 TO THE STRATEGIC TARGETS OF THE PARTICIPATING RIS? (GIVE EXAMPLES) USE THE SCALE WITH THE FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

Large. This demonstration gives the tools to implement multi-RI experiments with which several GD-RTS methods can be tested, for example, synchronous AC and asynchronous AC coupling.

11. HOW IMPORTANT IS DEMONSTRATION NO. 3 TO THE LAB STAFF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE PARTICIPATING RIS? (GIVE EXAMPLES) USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

Large. This demonstration presented a pioneering experiment which integrated the use of several tools developed in the project: VILLASnode, JaNDER, uAPI and CM tool. The lab staff learned how to use these tools for multi-RI experiments.

B.1.4 Multi-Energy District Flexibility

1. WHICH PROBLEM IS ADDRESSED IN DEMONSTRATION NO. 4?

DEMO4's objective is to examine the provision of power-to-heat services within a local multi-energy district and assess its influence on both the electric and thermal networks. To fulfil the flexibility requirements of the DSO, a combination of electric and thermal storage systems, along with flexible controllable loads like heat pumps, thermal loads, electric boilers, and more, can be utilised.

2. WHAT IS THE MOTIVATION FOR SOLVING THIS PROBLEM?

The widespread adoption of non-programmable RESs has presented significant challenges. To address these challenges, there is growing recognition that local energy systems with flexibility provision can offer viable solutions. This demonstration aims to explore the technical feasibility of providing power-to-heat services within a local multi-energy district. The primary focus is to assess the impact of such services on both the electric and thermal networks. In this context, the heating system can contribute to the electrical system by assisting in congestion management, which involves limiting electrical import and export, as well as providing balancing power when needed.

3. WHAT IS THE EXISTING STATE OF THE ART FOR SOLVING THIS PROBLEM?

The existing state-of-the-art for addressing the challenges posed by multi-energy districts and their complex systems typically involves the use of simulation, co-simulation, or HIL approaches for testing and experimentation. These methods are employed because replicating such complex systems in a single laboratory is often impractical. Researchers rely on these simulation techniques to analyse and assess the performance of multi-energy systems and their impact on electric and thermal networks. Simulation techniques offer a controlled and efficient means to study complex multi-energy systems, providing a safe and cost-effective alternative to real-world testing. Researchers can simulate various scenarios, assess the behaviour of the systems under different conditions, and explore potential solutions to optimise their performance. This approach is particularly essential in ensuring the viability and reliability of multi-energy districts in practical applications.

4. WHAT ARE THE ADDED VALUES OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 4 COMPARED TO THE STATE-OF-THE-ART IN TERMS OF (A) ACCURACY, (B) TEMPORAL RESOLUTION, (C) SCALABILITY,

(D) SCIENTIFIC EXPERTISE OF THE INVOLVED RIs, (E) SERVICES EXTENSIONS FOR THE INVOLVED RI/PARTNERS

The “Multi-Energy District Flexibility” demonstration introduces several added values compared to the state-of-the-art in various aspects:

- (a) **ACCURACY:** This demonstration enhances accuracy by enabling real hardware testing in a multi-energy district. Unlike traditional simulation methods that approximate real-world scenarios, this demonstration provides a higher degree of accuracy in assessing the performance and interactions of multi-energy systems. The use of actual geographically distributed hardware allows for precise measurement and validation of results, thereby improving the accuracy of assessments. This hardware is interconnected and synchronised using the software tools developed in the WP11-JRA2 and WP12-JRA3 and describe the associated deliverables.
 - (b) **TEMPORAL RESOLUTION:** The demonstration offers improved temporal resolution by providing a platform for geographically distributed real-time experimentation. Unlike simulations, which often operate at accelerated time scales, this approach enables researchers to observe and analyse multi-energy system behaviour in real-time while considering real-world phenomena that may be overlooked in simulations. This finer temporal resolution is critical for capturing dynamic interactions and responses within multi-energy districts.
 - (c) **SCALABILITY:** This demonstration addresses scalability by creating an extended RI that combines resources from different laboratories. This extended infrastructure has greater scalability compared to individual RIs. It enables the testing of multi-energy systems at larger scales, facilitating the evaluation of complex systems under more extensive and diverse conditions.
 - (d) **SCIENTIFIC EXPERTISE OF THE INVOLVED RIs:** The engagement of several RIs in this demonstration combines a wide range of scientific expertise from various domains, encompassing electrical and thermal fields, along with diverse user group experiences. This collaborative endeavour not only enriches the available scientific knowledge for addressing multi-energy district challenges but also fosters the inclusion of multiple perspectives and practical and theoretical insights, often specific to laboratory environments by playing a pivotal role in propelling research advancements in this field.
 - (e) **SERVICES EXTENSIONS FOR THE INVOLVED RI/PARTNERS:** The demonstration extends its services and capabilities to the participating RIs and partners. By offering a platform for real hardware testing and validation, it provides a highly valuable resource for research and development. This is demonstrated by the involvement of individuals external to the consortium in the Transnational Access (TA) activities. This expansion of services enables RIs and partners to thoroughly examine and validate their technologies and solutions within a more comprehensive and realistic environment than what can be achieved through simulator-based approaches. As a result, it fosters innovation and advances in the research of multi-energy systems.
5. PLEASE QUANTIFY THE TIME FOR CONDUCTION OF THE EXPERIMENTS OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 4! (DAYS OF LAB USAGE)

The time required for conducting the experiments of the demonstration primarily depends on the thoroughness of describing the experiment using the methods and concepts developed in WP10-JRA1, along with the validation tools from WP11-JRA2 and the soft-

ware tools provided by WP12-JRA3. Once the demo is accurately and comprehensively described, the experimental efforts can typically be summarised within a period of approximately 10 days. This time frame accounts for the preparation and execution of the experiments, as well as data collection and analysis.

6. PLEASE QUANTIFY THE TIME FOR PREPARATION OF THE EXPERIMENTS OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 4! (TIME TO EXPERIMENT IN DAYS)

The preparation of the experiments for demonstration, as previously described, can be a relatively time-consuming process. This phase, encompassing experiment planning, setup, and any necessary adjustments, can extend for a period of up to a couple of months. This time frame allows for thorough planning and ensures that all aspects of the experiments are meticulously arranged and optimised before the actual experimentation takes place.

7. HOW LARGE ARE THE CHANGES/IMPROVEMENTS OF THE PARTICIPATING RIs COMPARED TO THE SITUATION BEFORE? USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

The changes and improvements to the participating RI infrastructures brought about by the demonstration can be characterised as “large”, corresponding to level 4 on the scale. This demonstration has significantly enhanced the capabilities and functionalities of the involved RIs, resulting in substantial improvements compared to their previous state.

8. QUANTIFY THE COST-SAVINGS OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 4 COMPARED TO OTHER SOLUTIONS USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

The cost-savings of the demonstration compared to other solutions can be quantified as “moderate”, corresponding to level 3 on the scale.

9. WHAT IS THE STATUS (I.E., TRL) OF THE EXPERIMENT IMPLEMENTATION COMPARED TO THE STATE OF THE ART?

The status (TRL) of the experiment implementation in this demonstration compared to the state-of-the-art is at a TRL-6 level, indicating significant advancements beyond the current state-of-the-art.

10. HOW IMPORTANT IS DEMONSTRATION NO. 4 TO THE STRATEGIC TARGETS OF THE PARTICIPATING RIs? (GIVE EXAMPLES) USE THE SCALE WITH THE FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

The demonstration is of “moderate” importance to the strategic targets of the participating RIs. For example, it supports the strategic goal of enhancing research capabilities in multi-energy systems, which aligns with the RIs’ mission to foster innovation in energy-related research and development.

11. HOW IMPORTANT IS DEMONSTRATION NO. 4 TO THE LAB STAFF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE PARTICIPATING RIs? (GIVE EXAMPLES) USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

The demonstration is of “large” importance to the professional development of the lab staff at the participating RIs. It provides opportunities for staff members to gain hands-on experience with cutting-edge technologies and real-world experimentation, contributing significantly to their skill development and expertise in multi-energy systems research.

B.1.5 AC & ICT Co-Simulation

1. WHICH PROBLEM IS ADDRESSED IN DEMONSTRATION NO. 5?

Smart grids have evolved into complex systems characterised by mutual interactions and dependencies between the power system ICT components. To thoroughly assess the integration and validation of these systems at a systemic level, it is important to prioritise the development of simulation tools that can holistically model both power and ICT aspects. Currently, there is a notable absence of widely recognised cyber-physical approaches or software tools specifically tailored for effectively designing, analysing, and validating smart grid systems in this comprehensive manner.

2. WHAT IS THE MOTIVATION FOR SOLVING THIS PROBLEM?

The European ERIGrid 2.0 project addresses the challenge of system validation for smart grids through the development of a co-simulation-based approach. In ERIGrid 2.0, the software co-simulation is implemented using the Mosaik framework as a master, connecting all simulators (AC, ICT, and controller) through the Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI) standard. This demo aims to evaluate the accuracy achievable with this co-simulation approach. For this purpose, a case study on flexibility activation for voltage control is modelled using the co-simulation framework, and the simulation results will be systematically compared with hardware-based laboratory tests to measure the accuracy and effectiveness of the approach.

3. WHAT IS THE EXISTING STATE OF THE ART FOR SOLVING THIS PROBLEM?

Various approaches have been employed to model smart grids as cyber-physical systems. Some adopt comprehensive models that abstract both power systems and ICT subsystems at a higher level to avoid complexity in modelling the detailed aspects of each subsystem, but at the cost of accuracy. Others opt for specialised tools such as PowerFactory and PSS for the power system and NS-3 or OMNET for the ICT subsystem, which requires the development of interfaces between these subsystems, resulting in increased complexity, effort, and time consumption. Recently, co-simulation frameworks like Mosaik have emerged to act as interfaces between specialised simulators for ICT and power systems. However, these methods face challenges in terms of validation and there are currently further research activities in this direction.

4. WHAT ARE THE ADDED VALUES OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 5 COMPARED TO THE STATE-OF-THE-ART IN TERMS OF (A) ACCURACY, (B) TEMPORAL RESOLUTION, (C) SCALABILITY, (D) SCIENTIFIC EXPERTISE OF THE INVOLVED RIS, (E) SERVICES EXTENSIONS FOR THE INVOLVED RI/PARTNERS

The “AC & ICT Co-Simulation” demonstration

- (a) **ACCURACY:** The demonstration aims to characterise the performance of the co-simulation method and provide insights into its accuracy. This is achieved by conducting a comparative analysis between the results obtained from the co-simulation tool and those derived from physical experiments of the same system. Through this approach, the demonstration seeks to validate the reliability and precision of the co-simulation method by assessing its ability to replicate real-world scenarios and outcomes. The comparison between simulated and experimental data serves as a critical evaluation, offering a better understanding of the co-simulation tool’s effectiveness in capturing the dynamics of the physical system under study.

- (b) **TEMPORAL RESOLUTION:** The demonstration facilitates the characterisation and validation of the Mosaik co-simulation tool designed for modelling and simulating smart grid systems with close-to-real-time temporal precision. This capability offer researchers a quick and flexible setup, using well known specialised simulators, to model and study smart grid applications in finer temporal scales.
- (c) **SCALABILITY:** Mosaik, being a co-simulation platform, offers a distinct advantage in modelling larger and complex systems, presenting a more accessible alternative to physical laboratory setups. The characterisation and validation of this allows researchers to efficiently model large systems with a level of complexity that might be impractical in a physical experimental setting. By ensuring that Mosaik maintains comparable accuracy to physical experiments, researchers can leverage the platform's capabilities to explore and analyse complex dynamics in smart grid systems. This not only enhances the scalability of simulations but also provides a reliable and efficient tool for investigating real-world scenarios in a virtual environment.
- (d) **SCIENTIFIC EXPERTISE OF THE INVOLVED RIs:** The demonstrator engages researchers with expertise in both ICT and power system domains from two research institutions, facilitating collaborative experiments conducted across both premises/RIs. This interdisciplinary approach enables researchers from each domain to gain deeper insights and knowledge about the other, fostering a comprehensive understanding of the interdependencies and interactions between ICT and power systems within the context of smart grids. Moreover, the demonstrator serves as an educational platform, offering participants valuable insights into the effective utilisation of the co-simulation tool. Researchers can also explore potential error associated with the tool, providing a holistic learning experience and enhancing their proficiency in utilising co-simulation for complex cyber-physical system studies.
- (e) **SERVICES EXTENSIONS FOR THE INVOLVED RI/PARTNERS:** With the successful validation of the co-simulation framework, RIs can consider integrating the Mosaik platform into their testing tool portfolio for future applications. By incorporating Mosaik into their toolkit, RIs can enhance their capabilities in modelling and simulating complex cyber-physical systems, particularly in the domain of smart grids.

5. PLEASE QUANTIFY THE TIME FOR CONDUCTION OF THE EXPERIMENTS OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 5! (DAYS OF LAB USAGE)

The time required for conducting the experiments of this demo partly depends on the methods and use-case a description from WP10-JRA1, along with the methods developed in WP11-JRA2. There will be two experiments, one in each of the participating research infrastructures. Once the demo is accurately and comprehensively described, the two experimental efforts can typically be summarised within a period of approximately 15 days. This timeframe accounts for conduction of the experiments, as well as data collection and analysis.

6. PLEASE QUANTIFY THE TIME FOR PREPARATION OF THE EXPERIMENTS OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 5! (TIME TO EXPERIMENT IN DAYS)

The preparation of the experiments for the phase of this mode, encompassing experiment planning, setup, and any necessary adjustments, can extend for a period of up to a couple of months.

7. HOW LARGE ARE THE CHANGES/IMPROVEMENTS OF THE PARTICIPATING RIs COMPARED TO THE SITUATION BEFORE? USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE;

4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

The changes and improvements to the participating RI infrastructures brought about by this demo can be characterised as “moderate,” - level 3

8. QUANTIFY THE COST-SAVINGS OF DEMONSTRATION NO. 5 COMPARED TO OTHER SOLUTIONS USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

The cost-savings of DEMO5 compared to other solutions can be quantified as “large” - level 4 as the co-simulation tool will allow to model complex smart grid systems in a very cost effective way compared to physical experiments.

9. WHAT IS THE STATUS (I.E., TRL) OF THE EXPERIMENT IMPLEMENTATION COMPARED TO THE STATE OF THE ART?

The status (TRL) of the experiment implementation in this demo is TRL-5 - TRL-6.

10. HOW IMPORTANT IS DEMONSTRATION NO. 5 TO THE STRATEGIC TARGETS OF THE PARTICIPATING RIs? (GIVE EXAMPLES) USE THE SCALE WITH THE FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

This demo is of “moderate” importance to the strategic targets of the participating RIs as it facilitates the utilisation of cost effective tools to model and study future complex smart grid systems.

11. HOW IMPORTANT IS DEMONSTRATION NO. 5 TO THE LAB STAFF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE PARTICIPATING RIs? (GIVE EXAMPLES) USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

This demo holds a “moderate” level of importance in the professional development of laboratory staff and researchers at participating RIs. It offers valuable opportunities for researchers and staff members to gain hands-on experience in developing supporting tools, algorithms, and, most importantly, in setting up cyber-physical laboratory testbeds for real-world experimentation.

B.2 Questions Specific

B.2.1 Improved Stability and Accuracy for PHIL

1. QUANTIFY THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE STABILITY REGION FOR PHIL EXPERIMENTS WITH VSIDC COMPARED TO OTHER INTERFACE ALGORITHMS BASED ON STABILITY AND SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS.

500% compared to “LPF-based V-ITM method” – stability has been ensured for impedance ratio up to 5.

2. QUANTIFY THE IMPROVEMENT OF ACCURACY FOR PHIL EXPERIMENTS WITH VSIDC COMPARED TO OTHER INTERFACE ALGORITHMS.

0.39% for active power and 2.56% for reactive power.

3. HOW BIG ARE THE MAXIMUM ERRORS IN STEADY STATE ACTIVE AND REACTIVE POWER EXCHANGE AT THE PCC WITH VSIDC COMPARED TO THEORETICAL RESULTS? (TS D1.1)

At the stability limit, results are shown in the following table:

Metric	Feedback Filter	VSI (32%)
η_P	1.64%	1.25%
η_Q	11.35%	8.79%

4. HOW BIG ARE THE MAXIMUM ERRORS DURING TRANSIENT EVENTS REGARDING ACTIVE AND REACTIVE POWER EXCHANGE AT THE PCC WITH VSIDC COMPARED TO THEORETICAL RESULTS? (TS D1.2)

Accuracy during transients was not evaluated thoroughly, but the VSI presents a better accuracy at the stability limit.

B.2.2 Time Delay Compensation for GDRTS

1. QUANTIFY THE IMPROVEMENT OF ACCURACY (ESPECIALLY FOR GEOGRAPHICALLY DISTRIBUTED) HIL EXPERIMENTS FOR THE DATA-DRIVEN TIME DELAY COMPENSATION COMPARED TO STATE-OF-THE-ART:

As illustrated in Table 8, the GDRTS system (case 2) that is based on the proposed data-driven DDPG and LSTM aided agent exhibits remarkably low power and angular errors compared to those of the conventional GDRTS system (case 1) with fixed time delay compensation. This demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed data driven DDPG and LSTM aided agent in handling variable delays in GDRTS system, effectively equipping the system delay compensation with the ability to adapt to variable delays.

2. HOW BIG ARE THE MAXIMUM ERRORS IN STEADY STATE ACTIVE AND REACTIVE POWER EXCHANGE AT THE PCC FOR THE DIFFERENT TIME DELAY COMPENSATION METHODS? (TS D2.1)

The maximum errors in steady state active and reactive power exchange at the PCC for GDRTS system (case 2) that is based on the proposed data-driven DDPG and LSTM aided agent and the GDRTS system (case 1) with conventional fixed time delay compensation are listed in Table 8.

B.2.3 Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for Remote RI Testing

1. QUANTIFY THE INITIAL AND THE REPEATED SETUP TIME FOR CONDUCTING THE EXPERIMENTS IN THE DIFFERENT RIs.

The initial setup time includes all the time it takes to have an experiment operating properly. In this case, it took an average of 16 h. The repeated setup time contemplates the time it takes to make a configuration change in the experiment. In this case, it was of 2 h on average.

2. HOW LARGE ARE THE IMPROVEMENTS REGARDING THE MANUAL CONFIGURATION EFFORTS FOR THE CONDUCTION OF THE EXPERIMENTS IN THE DIFFERENT RIs? USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

Moderate. By means of the CM tool, an important part of the multi-RI experiment is kept in a Global Configuration file. This avoids repeating the same configuration in the

participating RIs and saves time due to human errors.

3. HOW LARGE ARE THE TIME SAVINGS FOR RE-CONFIGURATION (PARAMETER CHANGE) OF SOFTWARE CONTROLLERS IN THE DIFFERENT RIs?

Parameter changes related to the setup of the multi-RI experiment represent a time saving of at least 50 % in the case of an experiment with two RIs, since the changes are implemented only once in the Global Configuration file, and automatically generated for each RI by the CM tool.

4. HOW MANY PERSONS (INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY (IT)), ADMINISTRATIVE, TECHNICAL, SUPERVISORY) ARE NECESSARY FOR SETTING UP THE EXPERIMENTS IN THE DIFFERENT RIs? QUANTIFY THE REDUCTIONS.

On average, three persons were involved before the implementation and improvement of the tools used in this demonstration. A Power Systems researcher, an researcher with software and IT skills and one administrative employee, who was in charge of implementing the firewall rules to allow communications between laboratories. Thanks to the lab coupling tool JaNDER and the improvements made to VILLASnode to support the WebRTC technology, the administrative employee was not required anymore, since these lab coupling tools were able to use standard communication mechanisms which do not require to add firewall exceptions or other security-related rules.

B.2.4 Multi-Energy District Flexibility

1. QUANTIFY THE IMPROVEMENTS IN FLEXIBILITY OF SECTOR COUPLING OF THERMAL AND ELECTRICAL ENERGY IN THE PARTICIPATING RIs. USE THE SCALE WITH FOLLOWING FIVE LEVELS (5=HUGE; 4=LARGE; 3=MODERATE; 2=LITTLE; 1=NO).

The improvement in flexibility, categorised as “moderate”, holds notable significance for the strategic objectives of the participating RIs. This enhancement directly contributes to advancing research capabilities in multi-energy systems, aligning closely with the RIs’ overarching mission to drive innovation in energy-related research and development. By bolstering the coordination and optimisation of thermal and electrical energy usage, this level of improvement serves as a pivotal step toward achieving the broader strategic targets set forth by the RI.

2. QUANTIFY THE VIOLATIONS OF ELECTRICAL (ENERGY/POWER) LIMITS IN THE PARTICIPATING RIs. USE FOR QUANTIFICATION EITHER SUITABLE UNITS [kWh, kW] OR %.

There were no instances of violations observed in relation to electrical energy or power limits within the participating RIs. All systems operated within the designated limits without exceeding or breaching any thresholds.

3. QUANTIFY THE DEVIATIONS OF THE ELECTRICAL (ENERGY/POWER) EXCHANGE SETPOINTS AT THE PCC. USE FOR QUANTIFICATION EITHER SUITABLE UNITS [kWh, kW] OR %.

No deviations were observed in the electrical energy or power exchange setpoints at the PCC during the evaluation period. Any variations that may have occurred were so small that they were not appreciable or did not provoke any issues. All exchange setpoints remained consistent with the designated values without any significant variations or deviations.

4. HOW BIG ARE THE DEVIATIONS OF THERMAL SETPOINTS (ENERGY, TEMPERATURES) IN THE PARTICIPATING RIs? USE FOR QUANTIFICATION EITHER SUITABLE UNITS [kWh, °K] OR %.

The deviations of thermal setpoints (energy and temperatures) in the participating RIs were negligible. Any observed variations fell within a minimal range and did not significantly impact the overall performance or functionality of the systems.

5. QUANTIFY THE REDUCTION OF THERMAL AND ELECTRICAL POWER LOSSES IN THE PARTICIPATING RIs. USE FOR QUANTIFICATION EITHER SUITABLE UNITS [kW] OR %.

Due to hardware issues and logistical challenges in securing suitable time slots, particularly with multiple partners involved and limited lab accessibility, quantifying the reduction of thermal and electrical power losses in the participating RIs during the evaluation period proved challenging. However, it is important to clarify that the main focus of the demonstrations in WP13-JRA4 was not to showcase the magnitude of the services provided by the system. Instead, the primary objective was to demonstrate the practical application of services developed in WP11-JRA2 and WP12-JRA3 for interconnecting facilities and conducting real-world experiments with geographically distributed laboratories. In this regard, it is noteworthy that the tests of the services in WP11-JRA2 and WP12-JRA3 yielded excellent results and received positive feedback indicating their effectiveness in real-world scenarios. Therefore, although quantifying power loss reduction would have provided additional insights, its absence did not affect the validity or significance of this demonstration.

6. WHAT IS THE ADDITIONAL ELECTRICAL AND THERMAL CAPACITY USED IN THE EXPERIMENT COMPARED TO THE SINGLE RI EXPERIMENT? USE FOR QUANTIFICATION EITHER SUITABLE UNITS [kW] OR %.

To calculate the additional electrical and thermal capacity used in the experiment compared to the single RI experiment, we need to consider the combined capacity of the various components involved from each of the participating RIs.

Firstly, from the Heat Pump system (CRES), the nominal electrical capacity is provided as $S=18\text{ kVA}$ and $P=16\text{ kW}$. Additionally, the heat network from DTU contributes with a stack of 9 electrical flow heaters, each of 2.5 kW, totalling 22.5 kW. Furthermore, the Energy Storage Systems (ESS) from SINTEF include a converter with a nominal capacity of 50 kV A and a power amplifier of 200 kV A.

From the CHP system (RSE), the natural gas internal combustion engine has an electrical capacity of 50 kWe (kilowatt electrical) and a thermal capacity of 81 kWth (kilowatt thermal). Additionally, there are bidirectional converters with a capacity of 30 kV A each.

To calculate the additional capacity used in the experiment, we sum up the electrical capacities and thermal capacities separately from each of the systems mentioned above and compare them to the capacity of a single RI experiment. This will provide us with the additional capacity utilised in the experiment.

To summarise the additional electrical and thermal capacities used in the experiment compared to a single RI experiment:

- Electrical Capacity:
 - Heat Pump (CRES): 16 kW. Additional Capacity: 108.5 kW (approx. 85.7%).
 - Heat Network (DTU): 22.5 kW. Additional Capacity: 102 kW (approx. 82.0%).

- ESS (SINTEF): 36 kW. Additional Capacity: 88.5 kW (approx. 71.1%).
- CHP (RSE): 50 kW_e. Additional Capacity: 74.5 kW (approx. 85.7%).
- Total Electrical Capacity: 124.5 kW.
- Thermal Capacity:
 - Heat Pump (CRES): 30 kW_{th}. Additional Capacity: 131 kW (approx. 77.6%).
 - Heat Network (DTU): 50 kW_{th}. Additional Capacity: 111 kW (approx. 68.8%).
 - CHP (RSE): 81 kW_{th}. Additional Capacity: 80 kW (approx. 49.7%).
 - Total Thermal Capacity: 161 kW_{th}.

7. WHAT IS THE ADDITIONAL ELECTRICAL AND THERMAL CAPACITY EMULATED IN THE EXPERIMENT COMPARED TO THE SINGLE RI EXPERIMENT? USE FOR QUANTIFICATION EITHER SUITABLE UNITS [kW] OR %.

The additional electrical and thermal capacity emulated in the experiment compared to the single RI experiment is as follows:

- Additional Electrical Capacity: 88.5 kW (approx. 71.08% increase),
- Additional Thermal Capacity: 161 kW_{th} (approx. 100% increase).

8. WHAT IS THE ADDITIONAL ELECTRICAL AND THERMAL CAPACITY SIMULATED IN THE EXPERIMENT COMPARED TO THE SINGLE RI EXPERIMENT? USE FOR QUANTIFICATION EITHER SUITABLE UNITS [kW] OR %.

The additional electrical and thermal capacity simulated in the experiment compared to the single RI experiment is as follows:

- Additional Electrical Capacity: 36 kW (approx. 28.91% increase),
- Additional Thermal Capacity: 0 kW_{th} (approx. 0% increase).

B.2.5 AC & ICT Co-Simulation

1. QUANTIFY THE ACCURACY OF THE CO-SIMULATION COMPARED TO THE COMPARABLE LABORATORY SETUP. USE FOR QUANTIFICATION THE UNIT %.

Due to a higher than expected complexity of the test setup and the need to revise the implementation several times, only the first of two experiments could be conducted in time for the deliverable, and the comparison with the co-simulation results could not be performed yet. Hence, no meaningful accuracy metrics could be calculated at this point. It is planned to complete and publish the work within the ERIGrid 2.0 project; these planned future publications are expected to yield the quantitative results required for KPI evaluation.

With the clarity of hindsight, the project team believes that some of the KPIs of demonstration 5 should have chosen to relate to the development of capabilities, knowledge and joint infrastructure, instead of exclusively focusing on technical measurements obtainable only at the end of a fully complete and successful test campaign.

2. HOW LARGE ARE THE DEVIATIONS OF SERVICE DELIVERED FROM SERVICE REQUESTED (TCR1) FOR THE FOLLOWING VARIABLES? (A) OVERALL INTEGRAL ERROR [kWh], (B) MAXIMUM OVERALL SERVICE DEVIATION [kW], (C) MEAN OVERALL SERVICE DEVIATION [kW], (D) MAXIMUM INDIVIDUAL INTEGRAL ERROR [kWh], (E) MAXIMUM INDIVIDUAL SERVICE DEVIATION [kW] USE FOR QUANTIFICATION EITHER SUITABLE UNITS [kWh, kW] OR %.

See point 1. Quantitative results from the comparison between co-simulation and experiment are not available yet.

3. HOW LARGE ARE THE DEVIATIONS OF TIME TO RESTORE STEADY-STATE OPERATION AFTER A FAILURE EVENT IN THE COMMUNICATION DOMAIN (TCR2) FOR THE FOLLOWING VARIABLES? (A) TIME FROM OCCURRENCE TO DETECTION OF COMMUNICATION FAILURE [MS], (B) TIME FROM DETECTION OF COMMUNICATION FAILURE TO END OF DISTRIBUTION OF NEW SETPOINTS TO UNIT CONTROLLERS [MS], (C) TIME FROM RECEPTION OF NEW SETPOINTS AT UNIT CONTROLLERS TO (PHYSICAL) SERVICE RESTORATION [MS] USE FOR QUANTIFICATION EITHER THE UNIT [MS] OR %.

See point 1. Quantitative results from the comparison between co-simulation and experiment are not available yet.

4. HOW LARGE ARE THE DEVIATIONS OF TIME TO RESTORE STEADY-STATE OPERATION AFTER A FAILURE EVENT IN THE ELECTRICAL DOMAIN (TCR3) FOR THE FOLLOWING VARIABLES?

See point 1. Quantitative results from the comparison between co-simulation and experiment are not available yet.

5. TIME FROM OCCURRENCE TO DETECTION OF ELECTRICAL EQUIPMENT FAILURE [MS].

See point 1. Quantitative results from the comparison between co-simulation and experiment are not available yet.

6. TIME FROM DETECTION OF ELECTRICAL EQUIPMENT FAILURE TO END OF THE DISTRIBUTION OF NEW SETPOINTS TO UNIT CONTROLLERS [MS].

See point 1. Quantitative results from the comparison between co-simulation and experiment are not available yet.

7. TIME FROM RECEPTION OF NEW SETPOINTS AT UNIT CONTROLLERS TO (PHYSICAL) SERVICE RESTORATION [MS] USE FOR QUANTIFICATION EITHER THE UNIT [MS] OR %.

See point 1. Quantitative results from the comparison between co-simulation and experiment are not available yet.

Consortium

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